

School of GeoSciences

Dissertation

for the degree of

MSc in CARBON MANAGEMENT

***Enhancing Policy Coherence for Sustainable
Development in Zambia: An Integrated
Assessment Model (IAM)-Based Approach to
the Climate-Water-Energy-Food Nexus***

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of climate change on Zambia's hydro generation infrastructure, energy consumption, water consumption, crop patterns, and land use using the CLEWs (Climate-Land-Energy-Water) modelling framework. The research contextualises the water-energy-food (WEF) nexus amidst urbanisation, population growth, and climate variability, aligning with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, focusing on SDGs related to hunger, water, energy, and climate action.

Prompted by severe droughts depleting water reservoirs, reducing potable water, impacting livestock, and causing significant crop production declines, the study highlights the need for integrated policy responses. The research aims to foster policy coherence within Zambia's food-climate-energy-water nexus, assessing trade-offs, quantifying policy impacts, and identifying institutional shortcomings.

Comparative analysis of BAU (Business-As-Usual), NA (No Adaptation), and CAI (Climate Adjusted Infrastructure) scenarios reveals significant differences. By 2026, the BAU scenario shows hydroelectric power dominance, while the NA scenario shifts towards biomass due to reduced hydro reliability, increasing reliance on polluting sources. The CAI scenario indicates a diversified and resilient energy mix with solar and floating solar PV. By 2050, BAU maintains hydroelectric power dominance but faces emissions and cost challenges. NA exacerbates these issues, while CAI demonstrates reduced emissions and enhanced resilience through diversification, including solar PV, geothermal, and nuclear power.

The IPCC B1 scenario projects moderate land and water demand increases due to sustainable practices, whereas the A2 scenario shows severe constraints with significant agricultural land expansion and water demand driven by higher emissions and climate impacts. The A2 scenario necessitates extensive irrigation, reflecting decreased precipitation and increased evapotranspiration, while B1 benefits from technological advancements and improved water management.

Exploring biofuels as a transportation energy source, the BAU scenario projects a significant increase in emissions and water demand, while the Biofuel Adoption (BFA) scenario shows slight emission reductions due to fossil fuel displacement. However, the Increased Agricultural Demand (IAD) scenario reveals higher emissions due to intensified agricultural practices.

Stakeholder engagement underscores the need for diversified energy investments, improved water management, sustainable agricultural practices, and gender-sensitive energy policies. Recommendations include investing in renewable energy, enhancing irrigation efficiency, supporting biofuel production, and promoting international cooperation for technology transfer.

This study concludes that a diversified and resilient energy mix, integrated water management, and sustainable agricultural practices are crucial for Zambia's socio-economic stability and climate resilience. Future research should enhance data collection, expand stakeholder engagement, and develop detailed sub-sector analyses within the CLEWs framework to support integrated policy implementation.

Keywords: climate change, hydro dependency, water consumption, crop patterns, land use, Zambia, CLEWs framework, energy mix, WEF nexus, policy coherence, sustainable development.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym/Definitions	Description in Study Context
CLEWs	Climate Land Energy Water Systems
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IAM	Integrated Assessment Model
WEF	Water Energy Food Nexus
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
CLEWs Model	Integrated assessment framework examining interconnections between resource systems
Technology	In CLEWs, any asset performing energy conversion processes, from resource extraction to electricity distribution, including land cultivation and hydropower plants
Commodity	Essential in CLEWs, these carry energy and move between technologies. Categorized into Primary Fuel, Transmission Level Fuel, and End-Use Fuel
MINLND	Technology representing Land Resource
LND	Commodity representing Land
LNDMAIHR	Technology representing Rainfed Maize Cultivation
LNDGROHR	Technology representing Rainfed Groundnuts Cultivation
LNDMAIHI	Technology representing Irrigated Maize Cultivation
LNDGROHI	Technology representing Irrigated Groundnuts Cultivation
LNDRIHR	Technology representing Rainfed Rice Cultivation
LNDWHEHR	Technology representing Rainfed Wheat Cultivation
LNDRIHI	Technology representing Irrigated Rice Cultivation
LNDWHEHI	Technology representing Irrigated Wheat Cultivation
LNDFOR	Technology for Land Representing Forests
LNDBLT	Technology for Land Representing Built-Up Areas
LNDWAT	Technology for Land representing areas of Water Bodies
LNDOTH	Technology for Other Land Cover or Land Use in Zambia
CRPMAI	Commodity representing Maize Crop
CRPGRO	Commodity representing Groundnuts
CRPRIC	Commodity representing Rice
CRPWHE	Commodity representing Wheat
LFOR	Commodity representing Forests
LBLT	Commodity representing Built-Up Areas
LWAT	Commodity representing Water Bodies
LOTH	Commodity representing Other Land Cover
MINPRC	Technology that produces Rain
DEMAGRSURWAT	Technology accounting for Surface Water for Agriculture
DEMAGRGWTWAT	Technology accounting for Groundwater for Agriculture
DEMPWRSURWAT	Technology to account for cooling water from Surface Sources
DEMPWRGWTWAT	Technology to account for cooling water from Underground Sources
DEMPUBSURWAT	Technology accounting for Surface Water for Public Consumption
DEMPUBGWTWAT	Technology accounting for Groundwater for Public Consumption
WTRPRC	Commodity representing Precipitation Water

Acronym/Definitions	Description in Study Context
AGRWAT	Commodity representing Water for Irrigation
WTREVT	Commodity representing Water that is Evapotranspired
WTRGWT	Commodity representing Water for Groundwater Recharge
WTRSUR	Commodity representing Water in Surface Water Sources
PWRWAT	Commodity representing Water for cooling in Thermal Power Plants
PUBWAT	Commodity representing Water for Public Consumption
DEMAGRDSL	Technology representing Energy (Diesel) for Agricultural Equipment
DEMTRABIO	Technology representing conversion of crops to Biofuel
MINCOA	Technology representing Coal Extraction
MINBIO	Technology representing Biomass Extraction
IMPLFO	Technology representing Light Fuel Oil Imports
IMPHFO	Technology representing Heavy Fuel Oil Imports
MINHYD	Technology representing Hydro Potential
MINSOL	Technology representing Solar Potential
MINWND	Technology representing Wind Potential
MINGEO	Technology representing Geothermal Potential
MINURN	Technology representing Uranium Potential
PWRCOA001	Technology representing Coal Power Plant
PWRBIO001	Technology representing Biomass Power Plant
PWROCH001	Technology representing Light Fuel Oil Power Plant
PWROCH002	Technology representing Oil-Fired Gas Turbine (SCGT) - Heavy Fuel Oil in Zambia
PWRHYD00X	X=1: Large Hydropower Plant (Dam) (>100MW), X=2: Medium Hydropower Plant (10-100MW), X=3: Small Hydropower Plant (<10MW), X=4: Off-grid Hydropower
PWRPVU001	Technology representing Solar PV (Utility)
PWRTRN	Technology representing Electricity Transmission
PWRDIST	Technology representing Electricity Distribution
PWRPVR001	Technology representing Solar PV (Distributed with Storage) or Rooftop Off-grid
PWRWND001	Future Technology representing Onshore Wind
PWRGEO	Future Technology representing Geothermal Power Plant
PWRPVF001	Future Technology representing Floating PV
PWRNUC	Future Technology representing Nuclear Power Plant
AGRDSL	Commodity representing Diesel for agriculture
TRABIO	Commodity representing Biofuels
COA	Commodity or fuel representing Coal
BIO	Commodity representing Biomass
LFO	Commodity representing Light Fuel Oil
HFO	Commodity representing Heavy Fuel Oil
HYD	Commodity representing Hydro
SOL	Commodity representing Solar
WND	Commodity representing Wind
GEO	Commodity representing Geothermal

URN	Commodity representing Uranium
ELC001	Commodity representing Electricity from Power Plants
ELC002	Commodity representing Electricity after Transmission
ELC003	Commodity representing Electricity after Distribution

1. Introduction

1.1. Study Context

Introduced by the World Economic Forum in 2011, the water–energy–food (WEF) nexus addresses corporate concerns about resource shortages due to urbanisation, population growth, climate variability, and increased consumption (**Allouche et al., 2015, Cavalli and Vergalli, 2022, Adamovic et al., 2019**). **Terrapon-Pfaff et al. (2018)** highlighted the interconnected nature of water, energy, and food resources, viewing them as a unified system. They argued that sector-specific policies fail to manage conflicts or exploit beneficial interactions, potentially causing unintended consequences. The WEF nexus offers a holistic approach to addressing these interrelations (**Cavalli and Vergalli, 2022, Benson et al., 2015, Weitz et al., 2017**).

Biggs et al. (2015) integrated the nexus within the 2030 Agenda, revealing numerous explicit and implied interrelations (**Le Blanc, 2015, Mpandeli et al., 2024**). Academic scrutiny emphasised that effective development must tackle interrelated challenges, requiring stakeholder coordination, alliance formation, and avoidance of duplications (**Yumkella and Yillia, 2015, Sukhwani and Shaw, 2022**). This involves integrating all three sustainability aspects—society, environment, and economy—into a cohesive perspective (**Cavalli and Vergalli, 2022**). However, the 2030 Agenda provides limited guidance on the practical prioritisation of the 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) despite recognising their interconnectedness (**Breuer et al., 2023, UNDESA, 2016**).

Scholars have developed frameworks similar to Raworth's doughnut model (**Raworth, 2017**) and Rockström's planetary boundaries (**Richardson et al., 2023**), where external environmental limits (SDG 13 to SDG 15) encompass economic and human development (SDG 2, SDGs 6 to SDG 9, SDG 11, and SDG 12). Within these structures, SDG 16 and SDG 17 act as enabling goals, while SDG 1 to SDG 5 and SDG 10 are central to sustainable development efforts (**Niestroy, 2016**).

To realise the transformative potential of the 2030 Agenda and address its intricate synergies and trade-offs, substantial literature on SDG interconnections has been produced (**Cavalli and Vergalli, 2022**). Many publications do not explicitly address specific policy challenges, but a significant portion focuses on promoting policy integration and coherence (**Bennich et al., 2020**).

Mpandeli et al. (2018) argued that meeting nutritional, energy, and water needs while addressing climate change aligns with the 2030 Agenda's objectives, necessitating the protection of natural resources and mitigation of climate impacts. Four specific SDGs—SDG 2 (end hunger), SDG 6 (ensure access to sanitation and clean water for all), SDG 7 (ensure access to affordable, sustainable, and

reliable energy for all), and SDG 13 (take urgent action to combat climate change)—are interconnected (Campos et al., 2021, UN, 2016).

This research, aligned with the SDGs in the 2030 Agenda, explores the nexus of energy, food, climate, and water (Figure 1-1). It highlights the crucial role of governance and public policies in fostering sustainable development in Zambia (UN, 2016, Hirwa et al., 2021, Zhou et al., 2022). Like other nations, Zambia faces complex challenges from the interrelated factors of climate, water, energy, and food. Zambia's unique socio-economic and environmental context demands a focused examination of these connections to develop policies that align with global goals and local circumstances (Mpandeli et al., 2024).

In Zambia, the interconnection of water, energy, and food is crucial for advancing socio-economic objectives and realising the national Vision 2030. Zambia's Vision 2030 outlines the nation's long-term development goals, emphasising sustainable resource management and holistic strategies to address complex challenges (GWP, 2022, MoGEE, 2023).

Figure 1-1. Connections between climate, land, energy, and water systems (CLEWs) Nexus and relevant SDGs (source: (UNDESA, 2023))

1.2. Problem Statement and Rationale

Zambia faces severe challenges due to an unprecedented drought in the southern region. This prolonged dry spell has depleted water reservoirs, reducing potable water availability and grazing lands, thereby impacting livestock (reliefweb, 2024). Crop production, particularly maize, pulses, peanuts, pearl millet, and sorghum, has declined, affecting 1 million hectares of maize fields out of the 2.2 million hectares cultivated in the 2023/2024 season (reliefweb, 2024). Consequently, food prices have soared, impacting residents reliant on markets for sustenance (UN, 2024). Additionally, frequent

power outages (load shedding) have worsened the situation, affecting agricultural output, food processing, and economic activities (**Bwalya Umar et al., 2022**).

Despite the urgent need for collaborative efforts to address these interconnected issues, policy coherence remains lacking, hindering effective responses. Urban areas also face energy deprivation due to load shedding, disrupting daily life, commerce, and healthcare services (**Sakala, 2023**). In response, urban dwellers increasingly resort to biomass fuels like charcoal and firewood, contributing to deforestation, air pollution, and health risks. This exacerbates climate change effects and underscores the need for sustainable development measures (**Rawlins and Kalaba, 2020, MoGEE, 2023**).

This study examines essential resources such as energy, climate, water, and land. Globally, a quarter of adults face food security challenges, highlighting the urgent need to address these issues (**World Bank, 2019**). Zambia, among the world's least prosperous nations, struggles with food insecurity due to soil erosion, nutrient depletion, and inadequate water management (**WFP, 2018**). Despite efforts to increase maize production, persistent undernourishment remains, worsened by climate change projections (**World Bank, 2017**). Thus, focusing on food insecurity is crucial, aligning with the sustainable development principle of equitable land use.

Moreover, a quarter of the global population experiences water stress, emphasising the need for sustainable water management, especially in Zambia, where significant water scarcity exists (**FAO, 2017**). Many rural and urban communities rely on unsafe water sources (**FAO, 2020**). Addressing the energy deficit is also critical, with 10% of the global population lacking electricity access, mirrored by Zambia's 31% energy access issue (**Nyoni, 2022**). Zambia's heavy reliance on hydropower further exacerbates water stress (**Nyoni et al., 2021**). Recognising these challenges, the study underscores the importance of coordinated efforts to achieve climate goals, considering Zambia's vulnerabilities in food, water, and energy systems.

1.3. Aims

This study aims to employ the CLEWs modelling framework to guide Zambian policy development; it seeks to foster consistency, identify synergies, and resolve conflicts within the energy-climate-food-water nexus, as illustrated in **Figure 1-2**. The goal is to make significant progress towards achieving SDGs in Zambia.

Figure 1-2. CLEWs nexus demonstrating synergies, conflicts, and opportunities¹

1.4. Specific Objectives

- a) Conduct a customised assessment of the trade-offs and interconnections within Zambia's food-climate-energy-water nexus.
- b) Apply the CLEWs framework for a quantitative analysis of policy impacts on food security, water management, energy access, and climate resilience.
- c) Identify institutional shortcomings hindering policy coherence in Zambia, considering frameworks, finances, capacity, roles, data, and time constraints.
- d) Assess the effectiveness of policy recommendations from CLEWs in addressing challenges related to energy access, water scarcity, food insecurity, and climate change in Zambia.

1.5. Research Questions

1. What will be the impact on Zambia's hydroelectric power capacity and overall electricity generation costs if infrastructure investments proceed without accounting for anticipated climate change effects, as demonstrated by the recent droughts in Q1 and Q2 of 2024 and previous years?
2. What are the projected impacts of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) B1 and A2 climate change scenarios on water usage, crop patterns, and land use in Zambia?
3. Considering the SDGs and the Renewable Energy Strategy and Action Plan (RESAP) of 2022 alongside the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) of 2024, should Zambia commit to meeting its transportation energy needs with biofuels? RESAP targets biofuel production from maize,

¹ Adapted from the initial project proposal by the author, which led to this dissertation

cassava, and sugarcane by 2030, while the IRP anticipates significant electricity demand for agriculture through 2050, increasing crop yield and water demand.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Policy Landscape in Zambia

Zambia has developed a suite of strategic documents aimed at shaping policy across climate, land, energy, and water systems. The following presents an overview of pertinent policies for this study, along with their respective strategies and action plans:

2.1.1. National Adaptation Plan

The National Adaptation Plan (NAP) of 2023 defines Zambia's climate change adaptation strategy, focusing on enhancing resilience in food security, water availability, and energy systems (**MoGEE, 2023**). It prioritises risk reduction, adaptive strategies, and capacity-building across sectors. Developed by the Government of Zambia, the NAP offers a medium to long-term framework to address identified risks and vulnerabilities. It acknowledges the significant threats climate change poses to socio-economic development, natural resources, and livelihoods, especially in vulnerable sectors like agriculture, forestry, infrastructure, and water. The NAP aligns with national development plans and international agreements, including the National Development Plan, Vision 2030, Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC), SDGs, and the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). It supports the global adaptation goals of the Paris Agreement (**MoGEE, 2023**).

2.1.2. Nationally Determined Contributions

Zambia's NDC, submitted to the UNFCCC, seeks to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 47% from the 2010 baseline, amounting to a reduction of 38,000 Gg CO₂eq (**UNFCCC, 2021**). Core components include mitigation measures such as Renewable Energy, Energy Efficiency, Sustainable Agriculture, and Sustainable Forest Management. These measures aim to encourage alternative fuels, sustainable charcoal production, and enhanced cooking technologies to minimise wood fuel use. Additionally, the plan targets transitioning to alternative fuels, aiming for ethanol-gasoline and biodiesel-diesel blends by 2030. Emphasising rural electrification with sustainable renewable energy sources is intended to decrease emissions from fossil fuels (**UNFCCC, 2015**).

2.1.3. Integrated Resource Plan

Launched in February 2024, Zambia's IRP for 2024-2050 seeks to achieve universal electricity access by 2030 while supporting economic diversification. Emphasising a varied energy mix, the IRP integrates traditional sources and renewables to ensure reliable supply, optimise infrastructure investments, and develop domestic resources for energy security. It highlights environmentally responsible power generation, reflecting Zambia's commitment to addressing climate change and promoting social and gender inclusion. However, the plan's exclusive focus on electricity overlooks the entire energy system, indicating a significant gap (**MoE, 2024**).

2.1.4. Renewable Energy Strategy

RESAP (2022 – 2030) aims to revolutionise Zambia's energy sector by promoting renewable energy for environmental sustainability and economic growth. Aligned with global goals like energy security and climate change mitigation, it advances SDG 7 through targeted actions. By 2030, the plan aims to produce bio-ethanol and biodiesel from sugarcane, maize, and soya beans, ensuring clean, affordable energy, improving health, reducing poverty, and protecting the environment (**MoE, 2022**).

2.1.5. National Policy on Climate Change

Zambia's National Climate Change Policy (NCCP) aims to mitigate the effects of climate change on energy production and economic growth. Coordinated by the Ministry of National Development and Planning, it prioritises vulnerable groups, promotes stakeholder cooperation, and advocates a multi-sectoral approach. The policy aligns with climate initiatives and national development plans, providing a framework for institutional collaboration and coordinated action (**PMRC, 2017**).

2.1.6. National Green Growth Strategy

The National Green Growth Strategy (NGGS) for 2023-2030 aims for sustainable economic growth while minimising environmental impact. It emphasises circular economy principles, resource efficiency, and integrating climate considerations into planning. Aligning with Zambia's Vision 2030 and national goals in the Constitution, the NGGS supports global sustainability targets and reinforces commitments to the Paris Agreement and other Multilateral Environmental Agreements, ensuring the country's sustainable future (**MoGEE, 2024**).

The Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP) dedicates a specific pillar to environmental sustainability. It stresses the need for robust regulatory frameworks and broad policy reforms to meet environmental objectives. By emphasising green growth initiatives, it aims to transition towards a modern green economy (**MoFNP, 2022**).

Zambia faces energy poverty, inefficient water utilisation, and low agricultural yield, which exacerbate climate change effects on small-scale farmers. These challenges highlight the necessity for coordinated policy measures to effectively tackle environmental issues (MoGEE, 2024).

The alignment of the 8NDP, NDC, NGGS, and Vision 2030 is summarised in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1. Alignment of 8NDP, NDC and NGGS (source: (MoGEE, 2024))

2.2. Climate Change Interactions and Resources

This section examines the interactions between climate change and key resources in the WEF ecosystem. It highlights the need for comprehensive assessment frameworks and explores the effects of climate change on Zambia's agriculture, water, and energy sectors, using insights from the IPCC and Global Agro-Ecological Zoning version 4 (GAEZ v4) on anticipated changes in land use, crop patterns, and water usage.

2.2.1. Resource Management and Limits to Growth

Comprehending the development of the WEF nexus is crucial; the 1970s "Limits to Growth" concept underscored global interdependence, while the 1990s introduced integrated resource management to tackle shortages in food, energy, and minerals (Meadows et al., 2013, Ibsch et al., 2016). These viewpoints highlighted sectoral interconnections, laying the groundwork for comprehensive socio-environmental approaches. Frameworks like CLEWs enable integrated analyses of climate, land, energy, and water systems, assisting policymakers and researchers in devising strategies for sustainable resource management and climate adaptation (Optimus, 2024).

2.2.2. Climate Change Impacts in Zambia

Zambia's geographic location, socio-economic pressures, and low adaptive capacity make it highly vulnerable to climate change. Over the next 10 to 20 years, this could result in major GDP losses due to reduced agricultural output, increased energy crisis risks, higher healthcare costs, and deteriorating natural environments (**MoGEE, 2023, PMRC, 2017**).

Shifting rainfall patterns threaten 40% of Southern Africa's water supply, causing floods and droughts (**PMRC, 2017**). These changes complicate access to safe drinking water, increase waterborne disease risks, and burden women and girls with water collection (**PMRC, 2017, Hamududu and Ngoma, 2020**).

The agriculture sector, employing a significant portion of the population and greatly contributing to GDP, is highly susceptible to climate change. Fluctuating rainfall, rising temperatures, and extreme weather events reduce crop and livestock productivity, worsening food insecurity and poverty, especially among subsistence farmers (**Ngoma et al., 2021**).

Zambia's reliance on biomass and hydroelectric power faces disruptions from frequent droughts and floods, affecting electricity access and exacerbating economic challenges (**PMRC, 2017, Nyoni et al., 2021**).

2.2.3. IPCC and GEAZ Perspective on Impacts

The IPCC's climate change scenarios provide insights into future land use, crop patterns, and water usage in Zambia; under the **B1** scenario, which is characterised by technological advancements and sustainable practices, land use might shift towards afforestation, although urban expansion may challenge agriculture (**Brown, 2008, IPCC, 2013, IPCC, 2019**). Conversely, the **A2** scenario, marked by limited environmental cooperation and high population growth, predicts deforestation, land degradation, and land use conflicts. Adapting to new crop patterns and water demands is vital in both scenarios (**Brown, 2008, IPCC, 2013, IPCC, 2019**). These insights highlight the necessity for Zambia to prioritise water conservation, climate-resilient agriculture, and sustainable land management to mitigate climate change impacts and protect socio-economic and environmental well-being (**MoGEE, 2023, MoGEE, 2024, Pirani et al., 2024**).

GAEZ v4, developed by the FAO² and IIASA³, evaluates crop suitability and agro-climatic potential for Zambia's main crops—maize, sorghum, and millet—assessing yield ratios under optimal versus existing conditions (**FAO, 2021, GAEZ, 2024**). Due to rising temperatures and decreasing rainfall, Zambia's arable land has become less productive, necessitating drought- and heat-resistant crops for food

² Food and Agriculture Organization

³ International Institute for Applied System Analysis

security (Chapman et al., 2020). GAEZ v4 provides historical data and future projections for crop suitability and agro-climatic yield potential under climate scenarios RCP⁴ 8.5 and RCP 2.6, aiding policymakers in understanding climate impacts and developing mitigation strategies (FAO, 2021, GAEZ, 2024). Focusing on the top three crops at national and subnational levels, GAEZ v4 helps formulate strategies for sustainable agriculture and climate resilience, with crop evaluation results accessible through the GAEZ v4 data portal (FAO, 2021, GAEZ, 2024).

2.3. CLEWs-An Integrated Assessment Model

This section explores the evolution of the CLEWs nexus framework, integrated assessment tools, and the contextual application of CLEWs at national, regional, and global levels.

2.3.1. CLEWs Nexus Approach Evolution

The CLEWs framework, illustrated in **Figure 2-2**, has become a key tool for integrated policy analysis; it explores the interconnections among water, energy, and agriculture systems (Ramos et al., 2021). Its bottom-up approach identifies trade-offs and synergies, crucial for coherent policy development (Jaramillo, 2023). CLEWs offers a comprehensive understanding of the ripple effects of decisions across the nexus, surpassing isolated approaches (Hülsmann and Ardakanian, 2018).

Figure 2-2. Simplified CLEWs framework (source: (Zhou et al., 2022))

Since the 2010s, as the food-climate-water-energy nexus strategy has gained importance, the CLEWs framework has become pivotal (Ramos et al., 2022). Originating from a conceptual study of a biofuel chain, it has been applied in over 30 global contexts (Newell et al., 2019). Its integrated modelling

⁴ RCP – Representative Concentration Pathway

approach allows assessments at various spatial scales, enhancing our understanding of the complex interconnections within the nexus (**Ramos et al., 2021**).

2.3.2. Modelling Tools for Nexus Assessment

Various modelling tools are essential for nexus assessment, emphasising comprehensive analysis within the food-water-climate-energy nexus (**Popp et al., 2017**). Global integrated assessment models (IAMs) like IMAGE⁵ and GCAM⁶ offer frameworks to study global interconnections among agricultural, water, and energy systems, providing valuable insights for resource management and policy implications (**JGCRI, 2020, IIASA, 2020**). Local models like SPATNEX-WE are crucial for understanding regional nuances, using a partial equilibrium linear optimisation method to analyse water and energy dynamics (**Khan et al., 2018**).

The CLEWs framework is versatile, combining quantitative and qualitative methods for detailed analysis of micro-level interactions in agriculture, water, and energy systems. Unlike traditional IAMs, CLEWs employs a bottom-up approach and can be adapted to diverse geographies and economies, making it relevant to local nexus complexities (**Ramos, 2021, Ramos et al., 2022, Ramos et al., 2021**). CLEWs often uses the OSeMOSYS modelling framework (**UNDESA, 2023**), an open-source linear optimisation tool that identifies cost-effective system configurations, guiding investment and technology decisions (**OSeMOSYS, 2023, Martindale, 2023, Tan, 2023**).

The range of tools highlights the need for a balanced approach; IAMs provide a global perspective, while local models offer detailed granularity (**Ramos et al., 2022**). Integrating insights from both scales helps policymakers develop strategies that are globally informed and locally applicable, promoting sustainable resource management and policy coherence.

2.3.3. CLEWs Application Context

CLEWs has advanced from theoretical studies to practical applications, proving its effectiveness in fostering sustainable development and policy coherence; case studies from Ethiopia, Sierra Leone, Uganda, India, and Mauritius illustrate its impact at the national level by guiding policy formulation, advancing development goals, and fostering collaboration (**Howells, 2018, ACPC, 2018, Mofor, 2018**).

⁵ Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment

⁶ Global Change Analysis Model

In the early 2010s, CLEWs emerged as a collaborative initiative involving KTH⁷, SEI⁸, FAO⁹, UNIDO¹⁰, IAEA¹¹, IIASA¹², and UNDESA¹³; it began as an analytical tool to study resource system dynamics (**FAO, 2012, Welsch et al., 2014**). It has demonstrated flexibility in integrated assessments, using methodologies such as the Low Emission Analysis Platform (LEAP), the Water Evaluation and Planning System (WEAP), and the GAEZ¹⁴ platform for agricultural land use planning (**Howells et al., 2013**).

CLEWs has assessed transboundary river basins like Syr Darya, Sava, Isonzo/Soca, and Alazani/Ganykh using the TBNA¹⁵ methodology; this highlights its versatility in addressing cross-border challenges and fostering cooperation among nations sharing water resources (**De Strasser et al., 2016**). Despite growing recognition of the interconnectedness of land, energy, and water systems, policy formulation often occurs in isolation, neglecting critical interdependencies. Studies from Uganda reveal the drawbacks of such fragmented policies and advocate for a holistic approach essential for sustainable resource management and climate adaptation (**Sridharan et al., 2019, Sridharan et al., 2020**).

⁷ Royal Institute of Technology

⁸ Stockholm Environment Institute

⁹ Food and Agriculture Organization s

¹⁰ United Nations Industrial Development Organisation

¹¹ International Atomic Energy Agency

¹² International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

¹³ United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs

¹⁴ Global Agro-Ecological Zoning

¹⁵ Transboundary Nexus Assessment

3. Research Methods

3.1. Study Area and System Interactions

This study focuses geographically on Zambia, acknowledging the country's unique socio-economic and environmental context within the broader climate-water-energy-food nexus. The interactions within this nexus are illustrated in the country's CLEWs reference diagram, as depicted in **Figure 3-1**.

Figure 3-1. CLEWs reference diagram (CRD) for Zambia (CRD terminologies captured under acronyms)

3.2. Research Design

The research design was carefully crafted to meet the aims (section 1.3) and objectives (section 1.4); it integrated both quantitative and qualitative methods seamlessly. Using a mixed-methods approach (Ramos et al., 2022), the study combined qualitative analysis of policy documents and stakeholder interviews with quantitative modelling through the CLEWs framework. This approach offered a comprehensive understanding of the Climate-Water-Energy-Food nexus's complex interconnections (Howells et al., 2013, Hirwa et al., 2021), tailored to the Zambian context. Figure 3-2 outlined the step-by-step methodology, ensuring the research's aims and objectives were met with a coordinated approach.

Figure 3-2. CLEWs method framework for the Zambian study

3.3. Methods of Data Collection

The methodology employed a thorough framework, integrating both local and international sources for a detailed understanding of CLEWs. Essential context-specific insights into nexus dynamics were provided by Zambian data. When local data was lacking, global datasets from reputable organisations like the United Nations and Climate Compatible Growth were used (**Tan, 2023, Martindale, 2023, OSeMOSYS, 2021, OSeMOSYS, 2023, CCG, 2023, FAO, 2019, UNDESA, 2023**). The data collection process involved:

- Reviewing policy documents
- Conducting detailed interviews with key stakeholders
- Requesting data from stakeholders and accessing local nexus data from government websites
- Engaging stakeholders to develop scenarios

3.4. Stakeholder Engagement

The author proposed using a nexus action framework by **von Braun and Mirzabaev (2016)** for Zambia's WEF value chain, emphasising the importance of multi-sectoral stakeholder involvement. Engagement through emails, questionnaires, official letters, and virtual meetings guided data collection, assumptions, and scenario development. These interactions validated model inputs and outputs, contributing to the creation of an open-source CLEWs model and resulting in climate-compatible policy insights. Stakeholders included academia, utilities, regulatory bodies, development partners, ministries, farmers, professional associations, civic institutions, private sector entities, investors, climate negotiators, and existing WEF partnerships in Zambia.

3.4.1. Policy Needs and Responses

The analysis of Zambian policies involved literature reviews and interviews. Existing policies and identified needs informed the CLEWs model inputs, while model-based insights addressed policy gaps. This approach provided relevant insights and policy responses aligned with CLEWs principles, considering gender-sensitive sector development and enhanced energy, water, and food security.

3.4.2. Impact of Actors' Objectives on Modelling Outcomes

In Zambia's politically charged environment, interactions at the WEF-policy interface were anticipated. Organisational, sub-organisational, and individual actors had specific objectives, interests, power, and resources influencing model design, data selection, assumptions, and scenario development. Understanding stakeholders comprehensively and engaging both CLEWs-aligned and non-CLEWs-aligned stakeholders were crucial to anticipating potential influences on scientific outputs.

Figure 3-3. Proposed stakeholder engagement approach

Figure 3-3 illustrates the proposed stakeholder engagement approach, linking quantitative model formulation with qualitative dialogues. Engagement outcomes informed quantitative assumptions for CLEWs modelling during scenario development, as detailed in section 3.5.

3.5. Scenario Design

In scenario design, it is essential to differentiate between mitigation scenarios, aimed at reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and adaptation scenarios, which focus on modifying systems to counteract climate change effects; the baseline 'business as usual' (BAU) scenario serves as a benchmark for comparison. The BAU scenario represents a future where current trends persist without significant policy or behavioural changes, providing a basis for assessing mitigation and adaptation strategies.

Table 3-1 outlines the scenarios pertinent to the research questions in section 1.5. Each scenario presents a different future for Zambia. Comparing these scenarios with the BAU scenario highlights the effectiveness and feasibility of various strategies.

Table 3-1. Mitigation and adaptation aligned scenarios

Scenario Name	Scenario Type	Shorthand Name	Descriptive Implementation
Biofuel Adoption Scenario (2024-2030)	Mitigation Aligned	BFA	The adoption of biofuels for transportation aims to reduce GHG emissions by switching from fossil fuels to biofuels from crops like sorghum, maize, cassava , and sugarcane (for bioethanol), as well as groundnuts and soya beans (for biodiesel) ¹⁶ ; targets are 64.9 million litres of biodiesel by 2025 and 75.5 million litres by 2030. Similarly, bioethanol targets are 80.1 million litres by 2025 and 92.8 million litres by 2030. Post-2030 biofuel demand will align with a GDP growth rate of 3.5%.
Increased Agricultural Demand Scenario (2024-2050)	Mitigation Aligned	IAD	Increase agricultural electricity demand, especially for irrigation, to support the rising need for biofuels; from 2024 to 2050, annual wheat production is projected to grow from 175,000 to 15 million metric tonnes, maize from 3 million to 6 million metric tonnes, and soya beans from 329,000 to 3 million metric tonnes. Agricultural electricity demand is forecasted to reach 0.26 TWh in 2026, 9.5 TWh in 2030, 16.0 TWh in 2040, and 24.87 TWh in 2050. This scenario explores the potential for biofuels to replace petrol and diesel vehicles in Zambia.
No Adaptation Scenario (2024-2050)	Adaptation Aligned	NA	This scenario envisions a future without further climate change adaptation measures; for Zambia's hydroelectric power generation, it assumes existing infrastructure and practices persist despite rising climate variability and extreme weather events. To model the impact of climate change on seasonal water inflows, hydropower capacity factors are projected to decrease by 50% from November to April, reduce by 40% from May to July, and increase by 20% from August to October between 2024 and 2050.
Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure Scenario (2024-2050)	Adaptation Aligned	CAI	Involves modifying infrastructure investments to better withstand climate impacts, such as enhancing the resilience of hydroelectric power generation through new water reservoirs and integrating drought-resistant technologies like floating solar photovoltaics, wind, nuclear, and geothermal power.
IPCC B1 Scenario (2024-2050)	Adaptation Aligned	B1	Represents a future with sustainable practices and reduced emissions; adaptation efforts focus on enhancing agricultural practices, improving water management, and optimising land use to handle moderate climate impacts. Starting in 2035, each unit of land produces 12.5% more. Additionally, precipitation increases by 15%, irrigation water usage decreases by 15% and remains constant until 2050, and evapotranspiration, groundwater recharge, and surface water runoff all increase by 15% and remain constant until 2050.
IPCC A2 Scenario (2024-2050)	Adaptation Aligned	A2	Assumes a higher emissions trajectory with more severe climate impacts; adaptation strategies tackle significant challenges in agriculture, water resources, and infrastructure to manage increased stress and disruption. Starting in 2035, each unit of land produces 25% less. Additionally, precipitation decreases by 15%,

¹⁶ Cassava, sugarcane and soya beans are the primary crops considered for biofuel production under the [Renewable Energy Strategy and Action Plan of 2022](#)

			irrigation water usage increases by 15% and remains constant until 2050, and evapotranspiration, groundwater recharge, and surface water runoff all decrease by 15% and remain constant until 2050.
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[Appendix I](#) provides details of the CLEWs model development, including the model reference system, inputs, outputs, and assumptions.

3.6. Methods Limitation

The CLEWs methodology, while powerful, has limitations; it simplifies complex systems, relies on assumptions, and may overlook some policies (**Ramos et al., 2022**). It is prone to data errors and uncertainties (**Welsch et al., 2014**). Sensitivity analyses can assess robustness, but policies like awareness campaigns may not be fully captured if they don't directly impact technology economics (**WRI, 2015**). As CLEWs is predictive, conclusions should be drawn cautiously (**Engström et al., 2017**). It is meant to guide policy decisions, not forecast the future (**Ramos et al., 2019**).

4. Model Results

4.1. Model Validation

To validate the Baseline (BAU) results from the CLEWs model for Zambia from 2019 to 2023, data was gathered from various sources to compare with the model outputs as illustrated in **Table 4-1** below. This validation process ensures that the model results are within acceptable limits when compared to actual figures.

Table 4-1. CLEWs model validation (baseline results vs actual data)¹⁷

Validation Metric	Year	Model Output	Actual Data	Percentage Deviation	Source
Power Generation Capacity (GW)	2019	2.99	2.98	0.34%	(ERB, 2024)
	2020	3.03	3.01	0.66%	
	2021	3.34	3.32	0.60%	
	2022	3.34	3.32	0.60%	
	2023	3.83	3.81	0.52%	
Gross Energy Consumption (PJ)	2019	356.79	354.78	0.57%	(IEA, 2021)
	2020	361.75	360.08	0.46%	
	2021	388.05	385.14	0.76%	
Water Withdrawal (Billion m ³)	2019	6.64	6.70	0.90%	(FAO, 2024a)
	2020	12.64	12.75	0.86%	
	2021	15.92	16.00	0.50%	
	2022	20.41	20.60	0.92%	
	2023	25.13	25.40	1.06%	
Crop Yield - Maize (t/ha)	2019	2.78	2.80	0.71%	(FAOSTAT, 2023)
	2020	3.88	3.90	0.51%	
	2021	4.52	4.55	0.66%	
	2022	4.78	4.80	0.42%	
	2023	5.34	5.35	0.19%	
Area by Land Cover - Crops (1000 km ²)	2019	12.46	12.50	0.32%	(OECD, 2024)
	2020	13.21	13.30	0.68%	
	2021	13.87	14.00	0.93%	
	2022	14.54	14.70	1.09%	
	2023	13.03	13.10	0.53%	

¹⁷ This is not an exhaustive validation as the CLEWs model has several inputs and outputs

4.2. Model Baseline
 4.2.1. Energy Component

Figure 4-1 and Figure 4-2 shows the power generation and domestic energy production from 2019 to 2050 for the energy component of the CLEWs system¹⁸.

Figure 4-1. Annual power generation – BAU

¹⁸ Detailed visualizations for the business-as-usual CLEWs scenario for Zambia can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

Figure 4-2. Annual domestic energy production – BAU

4.2.2. Land Component

The area by crop and land cover type per annum from 2019 to 2050 for the BAU is illustrated in **Figure 4-3** and **Figure 4-4** respectively. **Figure 4-5** shows the annual crop yields for the same duration.

Figure 4-3. Area by crop per annum – BAU

Figure 4-4. Area by Landcover Type

Figure 4-5. Annual crop yields - BAU

4.2.3. Water Component

The water component of the model is illustrated by the annual water demand (**Figure 4-6**) and water balance¹⁹ (**Figure 4-7**).

Figure 4-6. Annual water demand by sector – BAU

Figure 4-7. CLEWs model water balance - BAU

¹⁹ The model water balance as indicated in Figure 3-1, is given by; **Water Precipitation + Irrigation = Evapotranspiration + Surface Run-off + Ground Water Recharge**

4.2.4. Climate Component

Figure 4-8 shows the total emissions by source for the BAU scenario.

Figure 4-8. Annual emissions by source

4.3. Climate Adaptation Scenario Outlook

This section presents combined results for the Business-As-Usual, No Adaptation²⁰, and Climate Adjusted Infrastructure²¹ scenarios in assessing the climate adaptation outlook for Zambia. **Figure 4-9** illustrates the annual power generation, **Figure 4-10** depicts the total annual emissions, **Figure 4-11** highlights the cost of electricity generation, and **Figure 4-12** shows the power generation capacity.

Figure 4-9. Annual power generation – BAU, NA, CAI

Figure 4-10. Total annual emissions – BAU, NA, CAI

²⁰ Detailed visualisations for the NA scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

²¹ Detailed visualisations for the CAI scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

Figure 4-11. Cost of electricity generation – BAU, NA, CAI

Figure 4-12. Power generation capacity – BAU, NA, CAI

4.4. IPCC B1 and A2 Scenarios

The IPCC scenario **A2** results are presented through figures detailing key metrics: area by land cover type (**Figure 4-13**), water demand (**Figure 4-14**), area for rainfed crops (**Figure 4-15**), area for irrigated crops (**Figure 4-16**), annual groundnut production (**Figure 4-17**), and annual groundnut yield (**Figure 4-18**)²².

Figure 4-13. Area by land cover type – A2

Figure 4-14. Water demand – A2

²² Detailed visualizations for IPCC A2 scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

Figure 4-15. Area for rainfed crops – A2

Figure 4-16. Area for irrigated crops – A2

Figure 4-17. Annual groundnut production – A2

Figure 4-18. Annual groundnut yield – A2

The IPCC scenario **B1** results are depicted below through figures highlighting critical aspects: area by land cover type (Figure 4-19), water demand (Figure 4-20), area for rainfed crops (Figure 4-21), and area for irrigated crops (Figure 4-22)²³.

²³ Detailed visualizations for IPCC B1 scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

Figure 4-19. Area by land cover type – B1

Figure 4-20. Water demand – B1

Figure 4-21. Area for rainfed crops – B1

Figure 4-22. Area for irrigated crops – B1

4.5. Feasibility of Biofuels

The biofuel feasibility results for the three scenarios—business as usual, biofuel adoption²⁴, and increased agricultural demand²⁵—are presented through figures detailing key metrics: total annual emissions (Figure 4-23), water demand for irrigation (Figure 4-24), area by crop (Figure 4-25), fuel import (Figure 4-26), crop production (Figure 4-27), and crop yield (Figure 4-28).

Figure 4-23. Total annual emissions – BAU, BFA & IAD

Figure 4-24. Water demand for irrigation – BAU, BFA & IAD

²⁴ Detailed visualisations for the BFA scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

²⁵ Detailed visualisations for the IAD scenario can be accessed via the [OSeMOSYS cloud platform](#)

Figure 4-25. Area by crop – BAU, BFA & IAD

Figure 4-26. Fuel import – BAU, BFA & IAD

Figure 4-27. Crop production – BAU, BFA & IAD

Figure 4-28. Crop yield – BAU, BFA & IAD

Table 4-2 illustrates the conversion factors and energy equivalence calculations for biofuels from various crops in 2050 **Table 4-3** presents the total biofuel production and energy content, highlighting their potential to replace petrol and diesel imports in the same year.

Table 4-2. Conversion factors and calculations with energy equivalence

Biofuel	Crop	Scenario	Yield (Million Tonnes)	Conversion Efficiency (Litres/Tonne) (Facts, 2023)	Biofuel Produced (Billion Litres)	Energy Content (PJ)	Petrol/Diesel Equivalence (REN21, 2018)	Petrol/Diesel Equivalent (Billion Litres)
Biodiesel	Soya Beans	IAD	3.00	205	0.61	19.74	1.3	0.47
Biodiesel	Soya Beans	BAU	0.83	205	0.17	5.46	1.3	0.13
Ethanol	Maize	IAD	6.01	400	2.40	50.97	1.7	1.41
Ethanol	Maize	BAU	7.39	400	2.95	62.68	1.7	1.74
Biodiesel	Groundnuts	IAD	0.38	205	0.078	2.50	1.3	0.060
Biodiesel	Groundnuts	BAU	0.38	205	0.078	2.50	1.3	0.060
Ethanol	Cassava	IAD	8.35	180	1.50	31.86	1.7	0.88
Ethanol	Cassava	BAU	8.34	180	1.50	31.80	1.7	0.88
Ethanol	Sorghum	IAD	0.051	380	0.019	0.41	1.7	0.011
Ethanol	Sorghum	BAU	0.040	380	0.015	0.32	1.7	0.0088
Ethanol	Sugarcane	IAD	11.22	70	0.79	16.64	1.7	0.46
Ethanol	Sugarcane	BAU	11.20	70	0.78	16.62	1.7	0.46

$$\text{Biofuel Yield (litres)} = \text{Crop Yield (tonnes)} \times \text{Conversion Efficiency (litres/tonne)}$$

$$\text{Energy Content (MJ)} = \text{Biofuel Yield (litres)} \times \text{Energy Content per litre (MJ/litre), where;}$$

$$1 \text{ litre of ethanol} = 21.2 \text{ MJ (REN21, 2018)}$$

$$1 \text{ litre of biodiesel} = 32.1 \text{ MJ (REN21, 2018)}$$

$$\text{Equivalent Petrol / Diesel Replaced (litres)} = \text{Biofuel Yield (litres)} / \text{Equivalence Factor}$$

Table 4-3. Total biofuel production and energy content

Scenario	Biofuel Type	Total Production (Billion Litres)	Energy Content (PJ)	Equivalent Petrol/Diesel (Billion Litres)
IAD	Bioethanol	4.69	99.50	2.76
IAD	Biodiesel	0.69	22.25	0.53
BAU	Bioethanol	5.24	111.09	3.08
BAU	Biodiesel	0.25	7.96	0.19

4.6. Stakeholder Engagement Responses

Table 4-4 outlines the planned engagement with 25 stakeholders, detailing scope and focus areas. **Table 4-5** highlights key findings on policy needs, urban planning, agriculture, and energy recommendations. **Table 4-6** covers coordination, policy harmonisation, and gender mainstreaming efforts. **Table 4-7** summarises feedback on scenario design, including climate considerations and alternative energy sources.

Table 4-8 addresses challenges and limitations faced during the engagement process.

[Appendix II](#) contains the questionnaire, responses, and quantitative data, providing deeper insight into the engagement process and collected data.

Table 4-4. Initial planned engagement of 25 stakeholders

Group	Stakeholder/ Name	Title	Focus Area	Influence	Priority	CLEWs Aligned	Decision -Maker	Comm. Method	Engagement Status
Ministry	MoE ²⁶	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter/ Email	Contacted
Ministry	MoGEE ²⁷	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter/ Email	Awaiting Response
Non-profit	CEEEZ ²⁸	Institution	Multiple	Low	Medium	Yes	No	Letter/ Email	Contacted
Ministry	MoA ²⁹	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter / Email	Awaiting Response
Farmer	Situmbeko Owen	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter	Contacted

²⁶ MoE – Ministry of Energy

²⁷ MoGEE – Ministry of Green Economy and Environment

²⁸ CEEZ – Centre for Energy, Environment and Engineering

²⁹ MoA – Ministry of Agriculture

Farmer	Geoffery Kaonde	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter	Contacted
Farmer	Nwanjilwa Bwalya	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter	Contacted
Farmer	Mirriam Lundazi	Farmer	Agriculture	Medium	High	No	No	Letter	Contacted
Non-profit	SNV ³⁰	Institution	Multiple	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Letter	Contacted
Non-profit	WWF ³¹	Institution	Multiple	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Letter	Contacted
Non-profit	ZARENA ³²	Institution	Energy	Low	Medium	Yes	No	Letter / Email	Awaiting Response
Non-profit	GHAZ ³³	Institution	Energy	Low	Low	Yes	No	Email	Contacted
Farmer	Mwauluka Lyambi	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Farmer	Mweene T Events	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Farmer	Mr. James	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Farmer	CM ³⁴	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	Yes	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Farmer	Twalumba Nyirongo	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	No	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Utilities	ZESCO	Institution	Energy	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter / Email	Awaiting Response
Academia	UNZA / Mr. Clement Sichimwa	Lecturer	Other	Medium	High	No	No	Email / Letter	Awaiting Response
Farmer	Chipeta Kaoma	Farmer	Agriculture	Low	High	No	No	Letter / Phone	Contacted
Academia	CBU / Dr Edna Kabala	Lecturer	Economy	Low	High	No	No	Letter / Phone	Awaiting Response
Ministry	LCC ³⁵	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter	Contacted

³⁰ SNV – Netherlands Development Organisation

³¹ WWF Zambia – World Wildlife Fund for Nature

³² ZARENA – Zambia Renewable Energy Agency

³³ GHAZ - Green Hydrogen Association of Zambia

³⁴ CM – Farmer opted to use initials

³⁵ LCC - Lusaka City Council

Ministry	MOHI ³⁶	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter	Contacted
Ministry	A2C ³⁷	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter / Email / Phone	Awaiting Response
Ministerial Agency	FRA ³⁸	Institution	Multiple	High	High	Yes	Yes	Letter / Email / Phone	Awaiting Response

Table 4-5. Summarised key findings and insights

Stakeholder	Key Insights and Policy Recommendations
MoHI	Integrate solar power in rural housing, address financing and maintenance issues, and promote solar/mini-grid solutions in urban areas. Increase funding and improve maintenance strategies.
WWF	Effective borehole drilling for rural water access, and urban water managed by local utilities. Promote integrated water management policies.
LCC	Address housing deficit, balance land use demands, and promote sustainable projects. Develop integrated urban planning policies.
Commercial Farmers	Diversify crop portfolios, explore agritourism, use renewable energy. Support agritourism and renewable energy access.
GHAZ	Invest in green hydrogen technology, raise public awareness, and strengthen clean energy policies. Develop green hydrogen policies and incentives.

Table 4-6. Coordination, policy harmonisation, and gender mainstreaming

Stakeholder	Key Insights and Policy Recommendations
CEEEZ	Coordinate efforts across sectors, harmonise policies, and promote sustainable agricultural practices. Harmonise sector policies and promote biomass and solar technologies.
MoE	Plan integrated drought management for agriculture, energy, and water. Incorporate climate resilience in energy policies and increase irrigation efficiency.
MoE	Promote gender equality, and address energy poverty through clean cooking solutions. Promote clean cooking access and gender equality in the energy sector.

³⁶ MoHI - Ministry of Housing and Infrastructure Development

³⁷ A2C – Alternative to Charcoal

³⁸ FRA – Food Reserve Agency

Table 4-7. Scenario design feedback

Theme	Stakeholder Emphasis
Climate Considerations	Integrate climate considerations into policy planning and use a multi-sectoral approach. Address the energy crisis and diversify the energy mix.
Alternative Energy Sources	GHAZ, CEEEZ: Solar energy adoption. Address energy vulnerability and diversify sources.
No-Adaptation Scenario	CEEEZ: Energy crisis concerns, reliance on hydropower, need for energy diversification. Develop clean cooking fuel access and sustainable financing.
Biofuel Adoption	MoE: Promote biofuel projects and energy mix diversification. Support local biofuel production and reduce import dependency.
Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure	MoHI, LCC, GHAZ, CEEEZ, Commercial Farmers: Develop climate-resilient infrastructure policies, increase social housing funding, and promote public-private coordination. Support green hydrogen technology and conservation farming.

Table 4-8. Challenges and limitations

Challenge	Description and Proposed Solutions
Data Quality	Inconsistent/outdated data. Prioritise consistent data collection and enhance data sharing protocols.
Participation	Limited stakeholder participation in some sectors. Broaden stakeholder involvement and improve engagement logistics.
Engagement Logistics	Scheduling conflicts and preparation time. Implement advanced scheduling and clear communication.
Diverse Perspectives	Varied priorities leading to conflicts. Use facilitated discussions and inclusive decision-making.
Communication Barriers	Technical jargon and cultural differences. Simplify language and employ culturally sensitive strategies.

5. Model Analysis and Discussion

5.1. Model Validation Analysis

The model's outputs were compared with actual data from credible sources for key metrics between 2019 and 2023 as presented in **Table 4-1**. The validation reveals the following insights:

Power Generation Capacity

The model's output for power generation capacity shows a very close alignment with the actual data reported by the ERB across all years, with deviations consistently below 1%. This indicates the model's reliability in forecasting power generation infrastructure accurately.

Gross Energy Consumption

The gross energy consumption figures from the model align well with the IEA data. The deviations are minor, staying well below 1%. The model's exclusion of air and sea transport modes did not significantly impact the accuracy of the overall energy consumption prediction.

Water Withdrawal

The water withdrawal data from the model is closely aligned with the FAO AQUASTAT data, with deviations ranging from 0.50% to 1.06%. This consistency demonstrates the model's accuracy in predicting water resource usage.

Crop Yield - Maize

The model's predictions for maize yield are highly accurate, with deviations below 1% across all years. This shows the model's strong capability to forecast agricultural outputs.

Area by Land Cover - Crops

The model accurately predicts the area under crop cultivation, with deviations consistently below 1.1%. This further validates the model's precision in land use projections.

The minor deviations between the model outputs and the actual data indicate the model's robustness and reliability in predicting various metrics essential for assessing Zambia's energy, water, and agricultural sectors. The validation exercise confirms that the model outputs are within acceptable limits, making the model a reliable tool for future projections and policymaking.

5.2. Model Baseline Analysis

Power Generation and Energy Production Analysis

Under the BAU scenario, Zambia's power generation remains predominantly hydroelectric from 2019 to 2050. **Figure 4-1** shows hydroelectric power increasing from 45.17 PJ in 2019 to 126.84 PJ by 2050, highlighting the system's vulnerability to climate variability. Biomass contribution, initially minimal, rises from 0 PJ in 2019 to 38.02 PJ by 2050, indicating a slow shift towards energy diversification. Coal usage peaks at 5.20 PJ in 2025, stabilises around 1.70 PJ by 2045, and drops to zero by 2049. Oil products have minimal impact, peaking at 1.04 PJ in 2050. Solar PV, both rooftop and utility, shows a gradual increase, with utility-scale solar growing from 0.01 PJ in 2019 to 2.02 PJ by 2050.

Overall, the energy sector trends towards diversification, though biomass and hydropower remain dominant, with minor solar contribution by 2050. **Figure 4-2** shows biomass production rising from 486.60 PJ in 2019 to 1569.79 PJ by 2050, while coal peaks at 60.37 PJ in 2045 before declining to zero by 2050, replaced by biomass after 2048.

Land System Analysis

Land use for crops, particularly maize, groundnuts, and cassava, expands significantly under the BAU scenario. **Figure 4-3** indicates maize cultivation increasing from 7.07 thousand km² in 2019 to 11.05 thousand km² by 2050. **Figure 4-4** shows corresponding crop yield improvements, increasing water (**Figure 4-6**) and energy demands for irrigation and processing (**Ali and Talukder, 2008**). **Figure 4-5** reveals forest area declining from 468.8 thousand km² in 2019 to 433.08 thousand km² by 2050, indicating deforestation due to agricultural expansion. This change impacts biodiversity and reduces the country's carbon sequestration capacity, contributing to higher atmospheric CO₂ levels (**Daba and Dejene, 2018**).

Water System Analysis

Figure 4-6 shows irrigation water demand rising steeply from 6.22 billion m³ in 2019 to 50.76 billion m³ by 2050, driven by expanding agriculture and population growth. **Figure 4-7** indicates an increase in evapotranspiration rates from 2024 to 2025. Cooling water demand for power stations grows to 1.56 billion m³ by 2050, reflecting thermal power generation expansion (**Figure 4-1**). This increase highlights the need for integrated water and energy management strategies.

Climate System Analysis

Figure 4-8 shows increasing CO₂ emissions from biomass, oil products, coal, and diesel for irrigation. Biomass emissions rise from 48.66 million tonnes CO₂e in 2019 to 156.98 million tonnes CO₂e by 2050, driven by increased biomass energy consumption. Emissions from oil products and coal also show upward trends, reflecting growing energy demands and industrial activities.

5.3. Integrated Analysis of Adaptation and Mitigation Scenarios

*Analysis and Response to Research Question 1*³⁹

In addressing the research question concerning the impact on Zambia's hydroelectric power generation capacity and total electricity generation expenses under varying infrastructure investments, a detailed comparative analysis of the **BAU**, **NA**⁴⁰, and **CAI**⁴¹ scenarios is conducted.

2026 Comparative Analysis

In 2026, the **BAU** scenario shows hydroelectric power as the dominant source, contributing 65.66 PJ, with minimal input from other sources such as biomass and solar PV. However, under the **NA** scenario (**Figure 4-9**), there is a significant shift with biomass contributing 10.85 PJ and hydro reducing to 47.33 PJ due to climate impacts, reflecting a heavy reliance on more polluting energy sources as hydro becomes less reliable. The **CAI** scenario maintains hydro at 64.61 PJ, with the introduction of solar PV and floating solar PV, contributing a combined 4.15 PJ, indicating a move towards a more diversified and resilient energy mix (**Nyoni et al., 2021**).

The CO₂ emissions under the **BAU** scenario are projected to be 70.8 million tonnes (**Figure 4-10**). In the **NA** scenario, emissions rise to 72.5 million tonnes, a 2.4% increase due to higher biomass use. In contrast, the **CAI** scenario keeps emissions at 70.8 million tonnes, indicating no significant increase due to balanced renewable integration.

The cost of electricity generation in the **BAU** scenario is \$13.8/MWh (**Figure 4-11**). This cost rises sharply to \$23.0/MWh in the **NA** scenario, a 66.7% increase, driven by higher fuel and operational costs associated with biomass and coal. The **CAI** scenario sees a more moderate increase to \$16.5/MWh, a 19.6% rise from BAU, reflecting initial investment costs in renewable technologies but promising long-term sustainability (**Way et al., 2022**).

³⁹ What will be the impact on Zambia's hydroelectric power generation capacity and total electricity generation expenses if infrastructure investments continue without adjusting to expected climate change effects, as evidenced by the recent droughts in Q1 and Q2 of 2024 and preceding years?

⁴⁰ NA – No Adaptation Scenario

⁴¹ CAI – Climate Adjusted Infrastructure

2050 Comparative Analysis

By 2050, the **BAU** scenario sees hydro maintaining its lead with 126.84 PJ (**Figure 4-9**), with negligible contributions from other sources. The **NA** scenario shows biomass reaching 78.55 PJ, with hydro at 91.36 PJ. The **CAI** scenario presents a highly diversified energy mix with significant contributions from hydro (105.68 PJ), solar PV (5.08 PJ), and nuclear (12.40 PJ).

CO₂ emissions in the **BAU** scenario are projected to reach 179.2 million tonnes (**Figure 4-10**). The **NA** scenario shows a 4.0% increase to 186.4 million tonnes. Conversely, the **CAI** scenario achieves a 5.5% reduction to 169.3 million tonnes from **BAU**, demonstrating the effectiveness of renewable energy in reducing emissions (**Ahmed et al., 2022**).

The cost of electricity generation in the **BAU** scenario is estimated to be \$40.6/MWh (**Figure 4-11**). The **NA** scenario sees this cost rise to \$52.7/MWh, a 29.8% increase. The **CAI** scenario shows higher initial costs at \$75.4/MWh, indicating significant investments in renewable infrastructure with potential for long-term sustainability (**Way et al., 2022**).

Hydro Dependency and Climate Resilience

Zambia's reliance on hydroelectric power presents significant challenges, as evidenced by the severe droughts in Q1 and Q2 of 2024, leading to extensive load shedding of up to 12 hours daily (**Kaseshya., 2024**). This highlights the vulnerability of the **BAU** scenario to climate variability. The **NA** scenario attempts to address reduced hydro capacity by shifting towards biomass, resulting in higher emissions and costs, demonstrating the unsustainability of this approach.

The **CAI** scenario offers a more balanced and sustainable solution. By diversifying the energy mix with investments in solar PV, floating solar, geothermal, and nuclear power, Zambia can enhance energy security and resilience against climate impacts. This approach aligns with the recommendations of the Integrated Resource Plan and National Green Growth Strategy of 2024, which emphasise the need for resilient infrastructure (**MoE, 2024, MoGEE, 2024**).

The **CAI** scenario emerges as the most sustainable pathway for Zambia to address its energy challenges. By investing in a diversified energy mix and climate-resilient infrastructure, Zambia can mitigate the risks associated with hydro dependency and achieve its SDGs. Therefore, Zambia should support strategic investments in renewable and resilient energy infrastructure (**MoFNP, 2022**). This approach not only ensures energy security but also promotes environmental sustainability and economic resilience (**MoE, 2024**).

Analysis and Response to Research Question 2⁴²

BAU vs A2 Scenario

Comparing the **BAU** and **A2⁴³** scenarios reveals significant differences in land use patterns due to varying assumptions about population growth, emissions, and environmental cooperation. Under **BAU**, land allocated to other uses increases from 247 km² in 2019 to 276 km² in 2050, an 11.81% rise (**Figure 4-4**). The **A2** scenario shows a smaller increase of 7.70% (**Figure 4-13**), indicating more severe constraints on land availability due to heightened competition and environmental stress. Forest areas decrease by 7.61%, from 468.8 km² to 433.08 km² by 2050, highlighting ongoing deforestation challenges.

The **A2** scenario projects a dramatic increase in agricultural land use, with crop areas expanding by 127.07% (**Figure 4-13**) compared to a 45.48% increase under **BAU** (**Figure 4-4**). This expansion aligns with studies suggesting higher emissions and climate impacts necessitate more agricultural land to sustain food production (**Smith and Gregory, 2013**).

Water Demand

Under the **BAU** scenario, water demand in agriculture steadily increases over time (**Figure 4-6**). In contrast, the **A2** scenario, assuming higher emissions and severe climate impacts, shows a much more pronounced increase. Water demand for irrigation rises from 6.22 billion m³ in 2019 to 70.78 billion m³ in 2050, a 1039% increase (**Figure 4-14**). This sharp rise is driven by a projected 25% decrease in land productivity starting in 2035, necessitating extensive irrigation. Additionally, a 15% decrease in precipitation, groundwater recharge, and surface water runoff from 2035 onwards intensifies reliance on irrigation.

Area by Crop (Irrigated and Rainfed)

Comparing **BAU** and **A2** scenarios reveals substantial differences in agricultural land use for rainfed and irrigated crops. Under **BAU**, rainfed agriculture consistently declines across all crop types, reducing to zero by 2030. The **A2** scenario sees a significant increase in irrigated crop areas, highlighting a strategic shift towards irrigation to maintain productivity (**Kumar and van Dam, 2013**). For example, irrigated maize in the **BAU** scenario increases from 0.96 thousand km² in 2019 to 11.05 thousand km²

⁴² What are the anticipated effects of the B1 and A2 IPCC climate change scenarios on water consumption, crop patterns and land utilisation in Zambia?

⁴³ A2 – Assumes a higher emissions trajectory with more severe climate impacts

in 2050 (**Figure 4-3**), a 1052% increase. In contrast, the **A2** scenario projects a 1436% increase, reaching 14.73 thousand km² by 2050 (**Figure 4-16**).

These trends indicate a strategic shift towards expanding irrigated crop areas to ensure food security amidst declining rainfed agriculture productivity (**Rosa, 2022**). The higher increase in the A2 scenario reflects the need to compensate for reduced precipitation and increased evapotranspiration due to higher emissions and severe climate impacts (**Karimi et al., 2021**).

Groundnuts Behaviour

Groundnuts exhibit a substantial increase in rainfed area post-2035 under the **A2** scenario (**Figure 4-15**), contrasting with maize and other modelled crops. The rainfed area for groundnuts increases significantly from 1.58 thousand km² in 2019 to 6.30 thousand km² by 2050, marking a 298.35% increase. This rise reflects a strategic adaptation to the constraints posed by the **A2** scenario. Meanwhile, the irrigated area for groundnuts also sees an increase of 374.13%, from 0.23 thousand km² in 2019 to 1.07 thousand km² by 2050. This increase is less dramatic compared to maize's increase in irrigated area of 1436% under the same scenario. Groundnuts, being more drought-tolerant than maize, sustain productivity under rainfed conditions even with reduced precipitation (**Singh et al., 2013, Chimonyo et al., 2020**).

Groundnut production rises from 0.13 million tonnes in 2019 to 0.38 million tonnes by 2050, reflecting a 188.85% increase. However, yields decline from 719.50 t/ha in 2019 to 542.91 t/ha by 2050, a 24.54% decrease, reflecting the impact of adverse climatic conditions on productivity (**Hatfield et al., 2011**). This yield decline is offset by the expansion in cultivated area, ensuring overall production remains high.

These factors make groundnuts a sustainable option under the stressed environmental conditions projected by the **A2** scenario, unlike crops like maize, which require irrigation to maintain productivity.

BAU vs B1 Scenario

Area by Land Cover Type

Comparing the **BAU** and IPCC **B1**⁴⁴ scenarios reveals insights into the impacts of sustainable practices and technological advancements on land use. Under **BAU**, land allocated for other uses increases from 247 km² in 2019 to 276 km² in 2050 (**Figure 4-4**), reflecting an 11.8% rise, driven by urbanisation and industrial development. The **B1** scenario projects a slightly higher increase to 278 km², representing a

⁴⁴ B1 – Represents a future with sustainable practices and reduced emissions

12.6% rise (**Figure 4-19**), due to sustainable development strategies and technological advancements enhancing land use efficiency.

Built-up areas expand similarly under both scenarios, from 0.9 km² in 2019 to 1.79 km² in 2050, representing a near doubling. This consistent growth underscores the pressure of urban expansion due to population growth and economic development (**Brown, 2008, IPCC, 2019**). Forest areas decrease from 468.8 km² to 433.08 km² (**Figure 4-19**), a 7.61% reduction, indicating ongoing deforestation challenges despite the emphasis on sustainability in the **B1** scenario.

The most notable differences are in agricultural land use. Under **BAU**, crop areas increase from 12.46 km² to 18.13 km² (**Figure 4-3**), a 45.48% rise, whereas the **B1** scenario shows a 29.36% increase to 16.11 km² (**Figure 4-22**). This smaller rise in **B1** is due to improved agricultural practices and better water management enhancing productivity (**Zahoor et al., 2019**).

Water Demand

The comparative analysis of water demand for irrigation under **BAU** and **B1** scenarios highlights the impacts of sustainable practices. **BAU** shows a dramatic increase in water demand, from 6.22 billion m³ in 2019 to 70.78 billion m³ by 2050, a 1039% increase (**Figure 4-6**). This exponential growth is driven by expanding agricultural activities and population growth.

The **B1** scenario shows a moderated increase, rising to 38.35 billion m³ by 2050, a 517% increase (**Figure 4-20**), reflecting the effectiveness of sustainable practices and technological advancements, such as improved irrigation technologies and better irrigation scheduling (**Upadhyaya, 2015, Mandal et al., 2020**).

Area by Crop (Irrigated and Rainfed)

Under the **BAU** scenario, rainfed agriculture for all crops declines to zero by 2030, indicating vulnerability to climate impacts⁴⁵. Even with sustainable practices in the **B1** scenario, rainfed agriculture follows a similar downward trend, suggesting the need for adaptive strategies to enhance water use efficiency and transition towards resilient farming methods (**Bennett et al., 2014, Altieri et al., 2015**).

In irrigated agriculture, both scenarios project significant increases, but the **B1** scenario shows more moderated growth. For example, irrigated cassava in **BAU** increases from 0.34 thousand km² to 1.12 thousand km² by 2050, a 233% increase, while **B1** projects a 195% increase to 1 thousand km² (**Figure**

⁴⁵ Assumes a shift by farmers from rainfed to irrigated practices due to a succession of droughts between 2015 and 2024

4-22). This controlled growth highlights the potential for enhanced productivity through sustainable practices (Kulkarni, 2024).

The area under irrigated maize also shows dramatic increases, underscoring its importance. Under **BAU**, the area grows from 0.96 thousand km² to 11.05 thousand km², a 1052% increase, while **B1** projects a 923% increase to 9.82 thousand km² (Figure 4-22). These trends reflect the positive impacts of improved water management and crop diversification (Vernooy, 2022, Cofie and Amede, 2015).

Analysis and Response to Research Question 3⁴⁶

This section compares the **BAU** scenario with the **BFA**⁴⁷ scenario, and the **IAD**⁴⁸ scenario, assessing the impacts on emissions, crop yields, and water demand.

BAU vs BFA Scenario

Emissions Analysis: In the **BAU** scenario, emissions are projected to escalate from 58.04 million tonnes CO₂e in 2019 to 179.16 million tonnes CO₂e by 2050, marking a significant increase of 208.7%. Conversely, the **BFA** scenario, which incorporates biofuel production, anticipates emissions rising to 175.20 million tonnes CO₂e by 2050, reflecting a slightly lower increase of 201.9% (Figure 4-23). This reduction is primarily attributed to the displacement of fossil fuels by biofuels, aligning with other studies (Nogueira et al., 2020).

Water Demand Analysis: Water demand for irrigation under the **BFA** scenario is projected to surge from 6.22 billion m³ in 2019 to 51.00 billion m³ by 2050, a rise of 720.3% (Figure 4-24). The **BAU** scenario shows a similar increase to 50.76 billion m³, up by 717.2%. The slight difference highlights the additional water requirements for biofuel crops, consistent with other studies emphasising biofuels' high-water usage (de Fraiture and Berndes, 2009).

Fuel Import Reduction: Figure 4-26 shows the reduction of fuel imports due to the adoption of biofuels, for instance in 2050, fuel imports reduce by 7.2% under the **BFA** when compared to **BAU**. Currently, Zambia relies heavily on imported petrol and diesel, contributing to economic vulnerabilities associated with fluctuating global oil prices and supply chain disruptions (Price, 2024).

⁴⁶ Should Zambia Adopt Biofuels for Transportation Energy Needs?

⁴⁷ BFA – Biofuel Adoption Scenario

⁴⁸ IAD – Increased Agriculture Demand Scenario

Comparison of BAU and IAD Scenarios

Emissions and Crop Production: In comparing the BAU and IAD scenarios, notable differences emerge in emissions (**Figure 4-23**), fuel imports (**Figure 4-26**), and crop production (**Figure 4-27**) metrics. The BAU scenario projects annual emissions rising to 179.16 million tonnes CO₂e by 2050, whereas the IAD scenario forecasts a sharper increase to 202.00 million tonnes CO₂e. The increased agricultural demand does not result in a proportionate increase in biofuel production, which explains the higher emissions under the IAD scenario. However, the potential for biofuel production under IAD is explored in the succeeding section.

Impact on Fuel Imports: The BAU scenario suggests a steady increase in petrol and diesel imports, reaching approximately 284.91 PJ by 2050 (**Figure 4-26**). In contrast, the IAD scenario projects a sharp increase to 291.67 PJ, reflecting the higher energy requirements for intensified agricultural practices (**Phiri et al., 2021**). These figures underscore the dependency on fossil fuel imports under current practices and the substantial potential for biofuels to offset these imports (**Popp et al., 2018**).

Comparative Biofuel Production from Soya Beans and Maize by 2050

The IAD scenario projects the production of approximately 615 million litres of biodiesel from soya beans by 2050, a significant increase of over 260% compared to the BAU scenario's 170 million litres (**Table 4-2** and **Figure 4-27**). This dramatic rise underscores the potential benefits of enhanced agricultural practices and targeted policies aimed at increasing biofuel crop yields including crops like sugarcane (**Figure 4-25** and **Figure 4-28**).

In contrast, maize is expected to produce around 2.4 billion litres of ethanol under the **IAD** scenario, whereas the BAU scenario forecasts a higher output of approximately 3 billion litres, representing a decrease of about 18.6% (**Table 4-2**). This reduction suggests that the **IAD** scenario's focus on diversifying and increasing the production of various crops might lead to slightly reduced ethanol yields from maize specifically, possibly due to the allocation of resources and land to other high-yielding biofuel crops.

Biodiesel Potential from Soya Beans and Groundnuts by 2050

The potential for biodiesel production from groundnuts remains consistent across both scenarios, with projections at approximately 78 million litres by 2050 (**Table 4-2**). This stability suggests that groundnuts can be a reliable source of biodiesel regardless of agricultural intensity. However, the dramatic increase in biodiesel from soya beans in the **IAD** scenario highlights the crop's responsiveness to enhanced agricultural practices and its potential as a primary biodiesel source.

Bioethanol Production from Various Crops by 2050

The **IA**D scenario shows robust increases in bioethanol production from several key crops. Cassava is projected to yield approximately 1.5 billion litres of ethanol (**Table 4-2**), slightly higher than the **BAU** scenario. Similarly, sorghum and sugarcane also show modest increases under the **IA**D scenario, reflecting the overall effectiveness of enhanced agricultural practices in boosting bioethanol yields. These increases are critical for meeting energy needs sustainably, as they provide substantial ethanol volumes that can significantly offset fossil fuel use.

Replacement of Petrol and Diesel Imports by Biofuel

The potential for replacing petrol and diesel imports with biofuels under the **IA**D scenario is substantial. The total energy content of bioethanol produced is approximately 99.5 PJ, and biodiesel production contributes an additional 22.25 PJ, summing up to a total of around 121.75 PJ (**Table 4-3**). Given that the total projected fuel import requirement by 2050 is about 291.67 PJ, the biofuels produced under the **IA**D scenario could theoretically replace approximately **41.7%** of the import needs. This potential suggests that Zambia could significantly enhance its energy security and economic stability by adopting biofuels.

Competition with Food Crops

To balance food and fuel needs, Zambia will need to adopt advanced agricultural practices, improve land use efficiency, and ensure sustainable water management (**Group and Management, 2009**). Innovations in irrigation efficiency and the development of climate-resilient crop varieties will be crucial in mitigating these challenges (**Hasanuzzaman, 2023**). Additionally, strategic planning will be essential to ensure that the increased biofuel production does not adversely affect food availability or environmental sustainability (**Renzaho et al., 2017**).

5.4. Stakeholder Analysis

5.4.1. Key Stakeholder Insights

The stakeholder analysis focused on 25 stakeholders, categorised into ministries, non-profits, farmers, utilities, and academia. Of these, 68% were successfully contacted, while 32% were awaiting responses. This distribution highlighted a broad spectrum of involvement across different sectors, reflecting diverse priorities and insights into sustainable development, energy security, and agricultural practices. The key insights from the interactions with stakeholders presented in **Tables 4-4** to **4-7** are summarised below.

Ministry of Housing and Infrastructure Development

- **Key Insights:** Emphasised the integration of solar power in rural housing projects to support vulnerable populations and promote sustainable urban planning. Collaboration with the Ministry of Energy on "solar village" projects like those in Matanda and Katamanda.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Increase funding for solar projects and improve maintenance strategies.

Ministry of Energy

- **Key Insights:** Concerned about the current energy crisis, the impact of drought on energy security, and the need for diversified energy sources. Promoted clean cooking solutions to address energy poverty and reduce dependence on charcoal. Emphasised the importance of gender equality in addressing energy poverty, advocating for clean cooking solutions that benefit women.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Incorporate climate resilience in energy policies, increase water-efficient irrigation, and promote access to clean cooking solutions.

Centre for Energy, Environment, and Engineering

- **Key Insights:** Stressed the need for coordinated efforts across sectors to manage natural resources efficiently, especially during droughts. Advocated for expanding the energy mix and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Harmonise sector policies and promote sustainable biomass and solar technologies

Lusaka City Council

- **Key Insights:** Highlighted the need to address the significant housing deficit exacerbated by urbanisation and competing land use demands. Promoted sustainable urban planning and stakeholder collaboration for waste-to-energy initiatives.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Develop integrated urban planning policies and promote sustainable projects.

Commercial Farmers

- **Key Insights:** Emphasised the importance of diversifying crop portfolios, exploring alternative revenue sources such as agritourism, and utilising renewable energy for sustainable agricultural development.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Support agritourism, enhance access to renewable energy, and promote water-efficient irrigation systems.

Green Hydrogen Association of Zambia

- **Key Insights:** Recommended investing in green hydrogen technology as a sustainable energy source, increasing public awareness, and leveraging international partnerships for technology transfer.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Develop policies for green hydrogen and strengthen clean energy incentives

5.5. Study Limitations

This study encountered several limitations, primarily related to data availability and quality, which influenced the precision of the model inputs. The complexity of the CLEWs framework necessitated certain simplifications, potentially omitting nuanced real-world interactions. Time constraints limited the depth of stakeholder engagement (**Table 4-8**), possibly excluding some crucial insights. These factors suggest that while the findings provide valuable direction, they should be interpreted as part of an ongoing iterative process. Further research is essential to validate, refine, and expand upon the initial results.

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

6.1. Conclusions

This study has addressed Zambia's severe challenges arising from unprecedented drought, impacting water reservoirs, grazing lands, crop production, and the socio-economic landscape. The CLEWs modelling framework was employed to analyse the intricate relationships within the energy-climate-food-water nexus, providing comprehensive insights for policy development.

The findings underscore the critical need for coordinated and sustainable policy responses to address Zambia's vulnerabilities. Model validation confirmed its robustness, with minor deviations from actual data, reinforcing its reliability for future projections and policymaking. The model's projections for power generation, water withdrawal, and crop yields indicate significant trends and potential strategies for sustainable development.

Responses to Research Questions and Stakeholder Insights

Question-1⁴⁹: The NA scenario's heavy reliance on hydroelectric power makes Zambia vulnerable to climate variability. In contrast, the CAI scenario's diversified energy mix with solar PV, floating solar, geothermal, and nuclear power proved more resilient, reducing emissions and ensuring a stable energy supply. This underscores the need for diversified investments to mitigate risks and achieve long-term sustainability.

Question-2⁵⁰: The B1 scenario projected sustainable land use and water consumption patterns, benefiting from improved agricultural practices and technological advancements. Conversely, the A2 scenario, with higher emissions and severe climate impacts, required extensive irrigation and increased agricultural land use, highlighting the need for adaptive strategies to ensure food security.

Question-3⁵¹: The IAD and BFA scenarios demonstrated significant potential for biofuel production, particularly from soya beans and maize, reducing reliance on imported fossil fuels. However, careful management is needed to balance food and fuel needs, emphasising advanced agricultural practices and efficient land use.

Stakeholder Insights: Key stakeholder insights stressed integrating solar power, promoting clean cooking solutions, and investing in green hydrogen technology. Emphasis on gender equality,

⁴⁹ Impact on Zambia's Hydroelectric Power Generation Capacity and Total Electricity Generation Expenses

⁵⁰ Anticipated Effects of B1 and A2 IPCC Climate Change Scenarios on Water Consumption, Crop Patterns, and Land Utilisation

⁵¹ Adoption of Biofuels for Transportation Energy Needs

sustainable agricultural practices, and public-private partnerships highlighted the multifaceted approach required to address these challenges.

Policy Recommendations

1. Diversify Energy Mix:
 - ✓ Invest in solar PV, floating solar, geothermal, and nuclear power to reduce reliance on hydroelectric power and enhance energy resilience.
 - ✓ Align infrastructure investments with climate change projections.
2. Improve Water Management:
 - ✓ Implement nationwide irrigation schemes and water-efficient systems to support agriculture.
 - ✓ Develop policies for rainwater harvesting and advanced irrigation technologies
3. Promote Sustainable Agriculture:
 - ✓ Encourage crop diversification and climate-resilient varieties
 - ✓ Support conservation farming and organic fertilisers to enhance soil health
4. Strengthen Partnerships and Collaboration:
 - ✓ Mobilise resources through public-private partnerships for renewable energy projects⁵².
 - ✓ Leverage international cooperation for technology transfer and capacity building.
5. Implement Gender-Sensitive Energy Policies:
 - ✓ Promote gender equality in energy access and decision-making.
 - ✓ Address energy poverty with clean cooking solutions to reduce reliance on charcoal and firewood
6. Adopt Biofuels:
 - ✓ Support biofuel production from soya beans, maize, and cassava to reduce fossil fuel imports.
 - ✓ Ensure biofuel production does not compete with food crops by improving agricultural practices and land use efficiency.

This research outlines a roadmap for addressing Zambia's challenges in energy, water, food security, and climate resilience. By adopting these policies, Zambia can achieve sustainable development, enhance socio-economic stability, and build resilience against future climatic uncertainties. An

⁵² This includes Green Hydrogen based on submissions by the Green Hydrogen Association of Zambia

integrated, multi-sectoral approach to policy development is crucial for a sustainable and prosperous future for Zambia.

6.2. Next Steps

Future research should prioritise enhancing data collection methodologies to improve model accuracy and reliability. Expanding the scope of stakeholder engagement to incorporate a wider array of perspectives is also crucial. Additionally, more granular sub-sector analyses within the CLEWs framework could yield deeper, more specific policy recommendations. Building partnerships with local and international organisations will be vital in refining the model and facilitating the practical implementation of integrated policies. These steps are essential to advancing Zambia's journey towards sustainable development and resource resilience.

References

- ACPC 2018. CLIMATE, LAND, ENERGY AND WATER STRATEGIES (CLEWS) TO SUPPORT THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONALLY DETERMINED CONTRIBUTIONS (NDCS) TO CLIMATE ACTION.
- ADAMOVIĆ, M., AL-ZUBARI, W., AMANI, A., AMEZTOY, A. I., BACIGALUPI, C., BARCHIESI, S., BISSELINK, B., BODIS, K., BOURAOUI, F. & CAUCCI, S. 2019. Position paper on water, energy, food and ecosystem (WEFE) nexus and sustainable development goals (SDGs).
- AFDB, A. D. B. G. 2023. *Zambia Economic Outlook* [Online]. Available: <https://www.afdb.org/en/countries-southern-africa-zambia/zambia-economic-outlook> [Accessed 24 May 2024].
- AHMED, I., REHAN, M., BASIT, A. & HONG, K.-S. 2022. Greenhouse gases emission reduction for electric power generation sector by efficient dispatching of thermal plants integrated with renewable systems. *Scientific Reports*, 12, 12380.
- ALI, M. & TALUKDER, M. 2008. Increasing water productivity in crop production—A synthesis. *Agricultural water management*, 95, 1201-1213.
- ALLOUCHE, J., MIDDLETON, C. & GYAWALI, D. 2015. Technical veil, hidden politics: Interrogating the power linkages behind the nexus. *Water Alternatives*, 8.
- ALTIERI, M. A., NICHOLLS, C. I., HENAO, A. & LANA, M. A. 2015. Agroecology and the design of climate change-resilient farming systems. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 35, 869-890.
- BENNETT, E., CARPENTER, S., GORDON, L., RAMANKUTTY, N., BALVANERA, P., CAMPBELL, B., CRAMER, W., FOLEY, J., FOLKE, C. & KARLBERG, L. 2014. Toward a more resilient agriculture. *Solutions*, 5, 65-75.
- BENNICH, T., WEITZ, N. & CARLSEN, H. 2020. Deciphering the scientific literature on SDG interactions: A review and reading guide. *Science of the Total Environment*, 728, 138405.
- BENSON, D., GAIN, A. K. & ROUILLARD, J. J. 2015. Water governance in a comparative perspective: from IWRM to a 'nexus' approach? *Water alternatives*, 8, 756-773.
- BIGGS, E. M., BRUCE, E., BORUFF, B., DUNCAN, J. M., HORSLEY, J., PAULI, N., MCNEILL, K., NEEF, A., VAN OGTRUP, F. & CURNOW, J. 2015. Sustainable development and the water–energy–food nexus: A perspective on livelihoods. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 54, 389-397.
- BREUER, A., LEININGER, J., MALERBA, D. & TOSUN, J. 2023. Integrated policymaking: Institutional designs for implementing the sustainable development goals (SDGs). *World Development*, 170, 106317.
- BROWN, O. 2008. The emission scenarios of the IPCC Special Report on Emission Scenarios (SRES).
- BWALYA UMAR, B., CHISOLA, M. N., MUSHILI, B. M., KUNDA-WAMUWI, C. F., KAFWAMBA, D., MEMBELE, G. & IMASIKU, E. N. 2022. Load-shedding in Kitwe, Zambia: Effects and implications on household and local economies. *Development Southern Africa*, 39, 354-371.
- CAMPOS, R., MELO, A. T. D., CAVES, L. & GARNETT, P. 2021. CES Winter School 2020. 'Sustainable development, complexity and change: thinking and practices for the SDG and other objectives'. Descriptive and evaluation summary report.
- CAVALLI, L. & VERGALLI, S. 2022. *Connecting the Sustainable Development Goals: The WEF Nexus: Understanding the Role of the WEF Nexus in the 2030 Agenda*, Springer Nature.
- CCG. 2023. *Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Starter Data Kit: Zambia* [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/7541227> [Accessed 19 November 2023].
- CHAPMAN, S., E BIRCH, C., POPE, E., SALLU, S., BRADSHAW, C., DAVIE, J. & H MARSHAM, J. 2020. Impact of climate change on crop suitability in sub-Saharan Africa in parameterized and convection-permitting regional climate models. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15, 094086.
- CHIMONYO, V. G., WIMALASIRI, E. M., KUNZ, R., MODI, A. T. & MABHAUDHI, T. 2020. Optimizing traditional cropping systems under climate change: a case of maize landraces and Bambara groundnut. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4, 562568.

- COFIE, O. & AMEDE, T. 2015. Water management for sustainable agricultural intensification and smallholder resilience in sub-Saharan Africa. *Water Resources and Rural Development*, 6, 3-11.
- DABA, M. H. & DEJENE, S. W. 2018. The role of biodiversity and ecosystem services in carbon sequestration and its implication for climate change mitigation. *Environmental Sciences and Natural Resources*, 11, 1-10.
- DE FRAITURE, C. & BERNDES, G. 2009. Biofuels and water. Cornell University Library's Initiatives in Publishing (CIP).
- DE STRASSER, L., LIPPONEN, A., HOWELLS, M., STEC, S. & BRÉTHAUT, C. 2016. A methodology to assess the water energy food ecosystems nexus in transboundary river basins. *Water*, 8, 59.
- ENGSTRÖM, R. E., HOWELLS, M., DESTOUNI, G., BHATT, V., BAZILIAN, M. & ROGNER, H.-H. 2017. Connecting the resource nexus to basic urban service provision—with a focus on water-energy interactions in New York City. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 31, 83-94.
- ERB, E. R. B. 2022. *Cost of Service Study (CoSS)* [Online]. Available: <https://www.erb.org.zm/electricity-cost-of-service-study-final-reports> [Accessed 24 May 2024].
- ERB, E. R. B. 2024. *Energy Sector Statistics* [Online]. Available: <https://www.erb.org.zm/statistics> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- FACTS, G. 2023. *Biofuel yields for different feedstocks and countries* [Online]. Available: <https://www.greenfacts.org/en/biofuels/figtableboxes/biofuel-yields-countries.htm> [Accessed 17 June 2024].
- FAO. 2012. *Global Agro-ecological Zones* [Online]. Available: https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/user_upload/gaez/docs/GAEZ_Model_Documentation.pdf [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- FAO. 2019. *AQUASTAT - FAO's Global Information System on Water and Agriculture* [Online]. Available: <https://www.fao.org/aquastat/en/> [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- FAO. 2020. *Pressure of water resources* [Online]. Available: <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en> [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- FAO, F. A. A. O. 2017. Water for Sustainable Food and Agriculture.
- FAO, F. A. A. O. 2024a. *AQUASTAT - FAO's Global Information System on Water and Agriculture* [Online]. Available: <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- FAO, F. A. A. O. O. T. U. N. 2024b. *Global Agro-Ecological Zoning version 4 (GAEZ v4) Data Portal* [Online]. Available: <https://gaez.fao.org/pages/data-viewer> [Accessed 15 May 2024].
- FAO, I. A. E. 2021. *The Global Agro-Ecological Zoning Platform version 4 (GAEZ v4)* [Online]. Available: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/313ec768e0964866b0e3ec5d720ab3b1> [Accessed 20 May 2024].
- FAOSTAT. 2023. *Crops and livestock products* [Online]. Available: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL> [Accessed 20 May 2024].
- FRANK, K. 2023. *Zambia Agri Market Update* [Online]. Available: <https://content.knightfrank.com/research/2630/documents/en/zambia-agri-market-update-2022-2023-10027.pdf> [Accessed 26 May 2024].
- GAEZ. 2024. *THE GLOBAL AGRO-ECOLOGICAL ZONING version 4 - Country profile: Zambia* [Online]. Available: <https://hqfao.maps.arcgis.com/sharing/rest/content/items/4b3a65d5583d47ffaf77d03ffc759178/data> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- GROUP, U. N. E. P. B. W. & MANAGEMENT, U. N. E. P. I. P. F. S. R. 2009. *Towards sustainable production and use of resources: assessing biofuels*, UNEP/Earthprint.
- GWP, G. W. P. 2022. *WEF Nexus key to advancing the socio-economic agenda in Zambia* [Online]. Available: <https://www.gwp.org/en/GWP-SouthernAfrica/About-GWP-SAF/more/News/wef-nexus-key-to-advancing-the-socio-economic-agenda-in-zambia/> [Accessed 14 May 2024].

- HAMUDUDU, B. H. & NGOMA, H. 2020. Impacts of climate change on water resources availability in Zambia: implications for irrigation development. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22, 2817-2838.
- HASANUZZAMAN, M. 2023. *Climate-Resilient Agriculture, Vol 2: Agro-Biotechnological Advancement for Crop Production*, Springer Nature.
- HATFIELD, J. L., BOOTE, K. J., KIMBALL, B. A., ZISKA, L., IZAURRALDE, R. C., ORT, D., THOMSON, A. M. & WOLFE, D. 2011. Climate impacts on agriculture: implications for crop production. *Agronomy journal*, 103, 351-370.
- HIRWA, H., ZHANG, Q., QIAO, Y., PENG, Y., LENG, P., TIAN, C., KHASANOV, S., LI, F., KAYIRANGA, A. & MUHIRWA, F. 2021. Insights on water and climate change in the greater horn of africa: Connecting virtual water and water-energy-food-biodiversity-health nexus. *Sustainability*, 13, 6483.
- HOWELLS, M. 2018. Climate, Land, Energy and Water strategies (CLEWs). *Stockholm*.
- HOWELLS, M., HERMANN, S., WELSCH, M., BAZILIAN, M., SEGERSTRÖM, R., ALFSTAD, T., GIELEN, D., ROGNER, H., FISCHER, G. & VAN VELTHUIZEN, H. 2013. Integrated analysis of climate change, land-use, energy and water strategies. *Nature Climate Change*, 3, 621-626.
- HÜLSMANN, S. & ARDAKANIAN, R. 2018. The nexus approach as tool for achieving SDGs: trends and needs. *Managing water, soil and waste resources to achieve sustainable development goals: monitoring and implementation of integrated resources management*, 1-9.
- IBISCH, R. B., BOGARDI, J. J. & BORCHARDT, D. 2016. *Integrated water resources management: concept, research and implementation*, Springer.
- IEA. 2021. *Zambia's Energy Mix* [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/countries/zambia/energy-mix> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- IIASA. 2020. *Applied Systems Analysis* [Online]. Available: <https://docs.messageix.org/projects/global/en/latest/overview/index.html> [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- IMF. 2020. *Annual Report* [Online]. Available: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/ar/2020/eng/> [Accessed 24 May 2024].
- IPCC. 2013. *Annex II: Climate System Scenario Tables* [Prather, M., G. Flato, P. Friedlingstein, C. Jones, J.-F. Lamarque, H. Liao and P. Rasch (eds.)]. In: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA. [Online]. Available: https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2017/09/WG1AR5_AnnexII_FINAL.pdf [Accessed 16 May 2024].
- IPCC. 2019. *Special Report on Climate Change and Land* [Online]. Available: <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl/> [Accessed 16 May 2024].
- IRENA. 2023. *Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2022* [Online]. Available: <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2023/Aug/Renewable-power-generation-costs-in-2022> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- IRENA. 2024. *Global Atlas for Renewable Energy* [Online]. Available: https://globalatlas.irena.org/workspace?_gl=1*14cnzo*_ga*NDAxNTI2NTU4LjE2OTg2MMDM4MjQ.*_ga_7W6ZEF19K4*MTcxNjE0MDYyOC40LjEuMTcxNjE0MTg2OC41OS4wLjA. [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- JARAMILLO, D. 2023. Analysis of climate, land and water strategies case of study for Ecuador. *zenodo*.

- JGCRI. 2020. *GCAM v7 Documentation: Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM)* [Online]. Available: <https://jgcri.github.io/gcam-doc/> [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- KARIMI, T., STÖCKLE, C. O., HIGGINS, S. S. & NELSON, R. L. 2021. Impact of climate change on greenhouse gas emissions and water balance in a dryland-cropping region with variable precipitation. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 287, 112301.
- KASESHYA, M. K. 2024. Zambian Government Extends Load Shedding to 12 Hours Amid Power Supply Crisis. *Melo Media Zambia*.
- KERNER, H., NAKALEMBE, C., YANG, A., ZVONKOV, I., MCWEENY, R., TSENG, G. & BECKER-RESHEF, I. 2024. How accurate are existing land cover maps for agriculture in Sub-Saharan Africa? *Scientific Data*, 11, 486.
- KHAN, Z., LINARES, P., RUTTEN, M., PARKINSON, S., JOHNSON, N. & GARCÍA-GONZÁLEZ, J. 2018. Spatial and temporal synchronization of water and energy systems: Towards a single integrated optimization model for long-term resource planning. *Applied Energy*, 210, 499-517.
- KULKARNI, S. 2024. Sustainable Cassava: A Case Study of Global Sustainability. *Global Sustainability: Trends, Challenges & Case Studies*. Springer.
- KUMAR, M. D. & VAN DAM, J. C. 2013. Drivers of change in agricultural water productivity and its improvement at basin scale in developing economies. *Water International*, 38, 312-325.
- LE BLANC, D. 2015. Towards integration at last? The sustainable development goals as a network of targets. *Sustainable Development*, 23, 176-187.
- MACROTRENDS. 2024. *Zambia GDP 1960-2024* [Online]. Available: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/ZMB/zambia/gdp-gross-domestic-product> [Accessed 23 May 2024].
- MANDAL, S., VEMA, V. K., KURIAN, C. & SUDHEER, K. 2020. Improving the crop productivity in rainfed areas with water harvesting structures and deficit irrigation strategies. *Journal of Hydrology*, 586, 124818.
- MARTINDALE, L. A., K; GARDUMI, F. 2023. *My first CLEWs Country Model* [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/8277193> [Accessed 10 December 2023].
- MEADOWS, D. H., RANDERS, J. & MEADOWS, D. L. 2013. The limits to growth (1972). *The future of nature*. Yale University Press.
- MOE, M. O. E. 2022. Renewable Energy Strategy and Action Plan.
- MOE, M. O. E. 2024. *Integrated Resource Plan* [Online]. Available: https://www.moe.gov.zm/irp/?page_id=15 [Accessed 15 May 2024].
- MOFNP, M. O. F. A. N. P. 2022. Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP) (2022 - 2026).
- MOFOR, L. 2018. Indicative climate, land, energy and water system (CLEWS) analysis for Sierra Leone-executive summ.
- MOGEE 2023. Ministry of Green Economy and Environment: National Adaptation Plan for Zambia.
- MOGEE, M. O. G. E. A. E. 2024. National Green Growth Strategy (2024-2030).
- MPANDELI, S., NAIDOO, D., MABHAUDHI, T., NHEMACHENA, C., NHAMO, L., LIPHADZI, S., HLAHLA, S. & MODI, A. T. 2018. Climate change adaptation through the water-energy-food nexus in southern Africa. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15, 2306.
- MPANDELI, S., NHAMO, L., LIPHADZI, S., MOLWANTWA, J. & MABHAUDHI, T. 2024. A WEF nexus-based planning framework to assess progress towards Sustainable Development Goals. *Circular and Transformative Economy*. CRC Press.
- NEWELL, J. P., GOLDSTEIN, B. & FOSTER, A. 2019. A 40-year review of food–energy–water nexus literature and its application to the urban scale. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14, 073003.
- NGOMA, H., LUPIYA, P., KABISA, M. & HARTLEY, F. 2021. Impacts of climate change on agriculture and household welfare in Zambia: an economy-wide analysis. *Climatic Change*, 167, 55.
- NIESTROY, I. 2016. *How are we getting ready? The 2030 agenda for sustainable development in the EU and its member states: analysis and action so far*, Discussion Paper.

- NOGUEIRA, L. A. H., SOUZA, G. M., CORTEZ, L. A. B. & DE BRITO CRUZ, C. H. 2020. Biofuels for transport. *Future Energy*. Elsevier.
- NYONI, K. J. 2022. The Zambian Energy Transition (ZET): A Case Study for OsemOSYS and FlexTool.
- NYONI, K. J. 2024a. A CLEWs-Based Approach to the Climate-Water-Energy-Food Nexus in Zambia.
- NYONI, K. J. 2024b. Model and Data Repository_CLEWs 4 Zambia.
- NYONI, K. J., MARONGA, A., TUOHY, P. G. & SHANE, A. 2021. Hydro-Connected Floating PV Renewable Energy System and Onshore Wind Potential in Zambia. *Energies*, 14.
- OECD, O. F. E. C.-O. A. D. 2024. *Land Cover in Countries and Regions* [Online]. Available: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- OPTIMUS. 2024. *Climate, Land (Food), Energy and Water strategies* [Online]. Available: <http://www.osimosys.org/> [Accessed 16 May 2024].
- OSEMOSYS. 2021. *GLUCOSE: An Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) for All - Global CLEWS 2021* [Online]. Available: <http://www.osemosys.org/glucoese.html> [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- OSEMOSYS. 2023. *Open Source Energy Modelling System* [Online]. Available: <http://www.osemosys.org/> [Accessed 10 December 2023].
- PHIRI, J., MALEC, K., KAPUKA, A., MAITAH, M., APPIAH-KUBI, S. N. K., GEBELTOVÁ, Z., BOWA, M. & MAITAH, K. 2021. Impact of Agriculture and Energy on CO2 Emissions in Zambia. *Energies*, 14, 8339.
- PIRANI, A., FUGLESTVEDT, J. S., BYERS, E., O'NEILL, B., RIAHI, K., LEE, J.-Y., MAROTZKE, J., ROSE, S. K., SCHAEFFER, R. & TEBALDI, C. 2024. Scenarios in IPCC assessments: lessons from AR6 and opportunities for AR7. *npj Climate Action*, 3, 1.
- PMRC, P. M. A. R. C. 2017. *National Policy on Climate Change* [Online]. Available: <https://www.pmrzambia.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/National-Policy-on-Climate-Change.pdf> [Accessed 15 May 2024].
- POPP, A., CALVIN, K., FUJIMORI, S., HAVLIK, P., HUMPENÖDER, F., STEHFEST, E., BODIRSKY, B. L., DIETRICH, J. P., DOELMANN, J. C. & GUSTI, M. 2017. Land-use futures in the shared socio-economic pathways. *Global Environmental Change*, 42, 331-345.
- POPP, J., KOT, S., LAKNER, Z. & OLÁH, J. 2018. BIOFUEL USE: PECULIARITIES AND IMPLICATIONS. *Journal of Security & Sustainability Issues*, 7.
- PRICE, Z. 2024. *Diesel Prices in Zambia: Trends, Influences, and Economic Impact* [Online]. Available: <https://www.zambiaprice.com/diesel-prices-in-zambia/> [Accessed 17 June 2024].
- RAMOS, E., HOWELLS, M., SRIDHARAN, V., ALMULLA, Y., DE STRASSER, L., ENGSTRÖM, R., MENTIS, D., TALLOTIS, C., GARDUMI, F. & PAPPIS, I. The Climate Land Energy Water systems (CLEWs) Framework: From mapping to models to research agenda's. *Geophysical Research Abstracts*, 2019.
- RAMOS, E. P., HOWELLS, M., SRIDHARAN, V., ENGSTRÖM, R. E., TALLOTIS, C., MENTIS, D., GARDUMI, F., DE STRASSER, L., PAPPIS, I. & BALDERRAMA, G. P. 2021. The climate, land, energy, and water systems (CLEWs) framework: a retrospective of activities and advances to 2019. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16, 033003.
- RAMOS, E. P., SRIDHARAN, V., ALFSTAD, T., NIET, T., SHIVAKUMAR, A., HOWELLS, M. I., ROGNER, H. & GARDUMI, F. 2022. Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems interactions-From key concepts to model implementation with OSeMOSYS. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 136, 696-716.
- RAMOS, E. P. S., VIGNESH; ENGSTRÖM, REBECCA 2021. Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems (CLEWs). *zenodo*.
- RAWLINS, J. & KALABA, F. K. 2020. Adaptation to climate change: Opportunities and challenges from Zambia. *African Handbook of Climate Change Adaptation*, 1-20.
- RAWORTH, K. 2017. *Doughnut economics: Seven ways to think like a 21st-century economist*, Chelsea Green Publishing.
- RELIEFWEB. 2024. *Zambia Drought 2024 - DREF Operation (MDRZM022)* [Online]. Available: <https://reliefweb.int/report/zambia/zambia-drought-2024-dref-operation-mdrzm022> [Accessed 14 May 2024].

- REN21. 2018. *Energy Units and Conversion Factors* [Online]. Available: <https://www.ren21.net/gsr-2018/pages/units/units/> [Accessed 17 June 2024].
- RENZAHO, A. M., KAMARA, J. K. & TOOLE, M. 2017. Biofuel production and its impact on food security in low and middle income countries: Implications for the post-2015 sustainable development goals. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 78, 503-516.
- RICHARDSON, K., STEFFEN, W., LUCHT, W., BENDTSEN, J., CORNELL, S. E., DONGES, J. F., DRÜKE, M., FETZER, I., BALA, G. & VON BLOH, W. 2023. Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science advances*, 9, eadh2458.
- ROSA, L. 2022. Adapting agriculture to climate change via sustainable irrigation: biophysical potentials and feedbacks. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17, 063008.
- SAKALA, M. 2023. Impacts of Load Shedding. *Daily Nation*.
- SINGH, A., NAKAR, R., GOSWAMI, N., KALARIYA, K., CHAKRABORTY, K. & SINGH, M. 2013. Water deficit stress and its management in groundnut. *Physiology of Nutrition and Environmental Stresses on Crop Productivity*, 14, 371-465.
- SITKO, N. J. & CHAMBERLIN, J. 2016. The geography of Zambia's customary land: Assessing the prospects for smallholder development. *Land Use Policy*, 55, 49-60.
- SMITH, P. & GREGORY, P. J. 2013. Climate change and sustainable food production. *Proceedings of the nutrition society*, 72, 21-28.
- SRIDHARAN, V., PEREIRA RAMOS, E., ZEPEDA, E., BOEHLERT, B., SHIVAKUMAR, A., TALLOTIS, C. & HOWELLS, M. 2019. The impact of climate change on crop production in Uganda—an integrated systems assessment with water and energy implications. *Water*, 11, 1805.
- SRIDHARAN, V., SHIVAKUMAR, A., NIET, T., RAMOS, E. P. & HOWELLS, M. 2020. Land, energy and water resource management and its impact on GHG emissions, electricity supply and food production—Insights from a Ugandan case study. *Environmental Research Communications*, 2, 085003.
- STADTBÄUMER, C., RUESINK, B. & GRONAU, S. 2022. Climate change scenarios in Zambia: modeling farmers' adaptation. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 11, 52.
- STAFFELL, I. & PFENNINGER, S. 2016. Renewables. *ninja*. URI: <https://www.renewables.ninja/> (visited on 05/10/2018).
- SUKHWANI, V. & SHAW, R. 2022. An integrated governance approach towards a water-energy-food nexus and climate change. *Handbook on Climate Change and Disasters*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- TAN, N. V., IOANNIS; LUSCOMBE, HANNAH; RICHARDSON, EMMA; MARTINDALE, LEIGH; ALEXANDER, KANE; FOSTER, VIVIEN; HOWELLS, MARK; HARRISON, JOHN 2023. Data to Deal: Developing an Energy Modelling Analytical Workflow to Enhance Political and Financial Decisions. *zenodo*.
- TERRAPON-PFAFF, J., ORTIZ, W., DIENST, C. & GRÖNE, M.-C. 2018. Energising the WEF nexus to enhance sustainable development at local level. *Journal of environmental management*, 223, 409-416.
- UN 2016. THE 2030 AGENDA FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.
- UN. 2024. *Zambia: Drought Response Appeal May 2024 - December 2024 (May 2024)* [Online]. Available: <https://zambia.un.org/en/268038-zambia-drought-response-appeal-may-2024-december-2024-may-2024> [Accessed 14 May 2024].
- UNDESA. 2016. *Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* [Online]. Available: <https://stg-wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/11125/unepswiosm1inf7sdg.pdf?sequence=1> [Accessed 14 May 2024].
- UNDESA. 2023. *GLOBAL CLIMATE, LAND, ENERGY & WATER STRATEGIES* [Online]. Available: <https://unite.un.org/sites/unite.un.org/files/app-globalclews-v-1-0/landingpage.html> [Accessed 10 December 2023].

- UNFCCC 2015. ZAMBIA'S INTENDED NATIONALLY DETERMINED CONTRIBUTION (INDC) TO THE 2015 AGREEMENT ON CLIMATE CHANGE.
- UNFCCC. 2021. *Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) of Zambia for the timeframe 2015-2030* [Online]. Available: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/Final%20Zambia_Revised%20and%20Updated_NDC_2021_.pdf [Accessed 15 May 2024].
- UPADHYAYA, A. 2015. Water management technologies in agriculture: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of AgriSearch*, 2.
- VERNOOY, R. 2022. Does crop diversification lead to climate-related resilience? Improving the theory through insights on practice. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 46, 877-901.
- VON BRAUN, J. & MIRZABAEV, A. 2016. Nexus scientific research: Theory and approach serving sustainable development. *The Water, Food, Energy and Climate Nexus*. Routledge.
- WAY, R., IVES, M. C., MEALY, P. & FARMER, J. D. 2022. Empirically grounded technology forecasts and the energy transition. *Joule*, 6, 2057-2082.
- WEITZ, N., STRAMBO, C., KEMP-BENEDICT, E. & NILSSON, M. 2017. Closing the governance gaps in the water-energy-food nexus: Insights from integrative governance. *Global Environmental Change*, 45, 165-173.
- WELSCH, M., HERMANN, S., HOWELLS, M., ROGNER, H. H., YOUNG, C., RAMMA, I., BAZILIAN, M., FISCHER, G., ALFSTAD, T. & GIELEN, D. 2014. Adding value with CLEWS—Modelling the energy system and its interdependencies for Mauritius. *Applied energy*, 113, 1434-1445.
- WFP, W. F. P. 2018. *Saving Lives Changing Lives* [Online]. Available: <https://www.wfp.org/countries/zambia> [Accessed 16 December 2023].
- WORLD BANK, D. 2023. *The Global Wind Atlas: A High-Resolution Dataset of Climatologies and Associated Web-Based Application* [Online]. Available: <https://globalwindatlas.info/en/area/Zambia#> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- WORLD BANK, T. W. B. G. 2017. *Climate-Smart Agriculture: Solutions to Reducing Poverty and Food Insecurity in Zambia* [Online]. Available: Climate-Smart Agriculture: Solutions to Reducing Poverty and Food Insecurity in Zambia [Accessed 17 December 2023].
- WORLD BANK, T. W. B. G. 2019. *Zambia Agriculture Investment Plan Supports Climate-Smart Agricultural Development* [Online]. Available: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/zambia/publication/zambia-agriculture-investment-plan-supports-climate-smart-agricultural-development> [Accessed 16 December 2023].
- WORLD BANK, T. W. B. G. 2022. *GDP growth (annual %) - Zambia* [Online]. Available: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=CNSintecho-ZM> [Accessed 24 May 2024].
- WORLD BANK, T. W. B. G. 2024. *Zambia's Climatology* [Online]. Available: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/zambia/climate-data-historical> [Accessed 19 May 2024].
- WPR, W. P. R. 2024. *Zambia Population 2024* [Online]. Available: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/countries/zambia-population> [Accessed 24 May 2024].
- WRI, W. R. I. 2015. *Avoiding Bioenergy Competition for Food Crops and Land* [Online]. Available: <https://www.wri.org/research/avoiding-bioenergy-competition-food-crops-and-land> [Accessed 16 December 2023].
- YUMKELLA, K. & YILLIA, P. 2015. Framing the water-energy nexus for the post-2015 development agenda. *Aquatic Procedia*, 5, 8-12.
- ZAHOOR, S. A., AHMAD, S., AHMAD, A., WAJID, A., KHALIQ, T., MUBEEN, M., HUSSAIN, S., DIN, M. S. U., AMIN, A. & AWAIS, M. 2019. Improving water use efficiency in agronomic crop production. *Agronomic Crops: Volume 2: Management Practices*, 13-29.
- ZAMBSTATS. 2013. *2010 CENSUS OF POPULATION AND HOUSING: Population and Demographic Projections 2011 - 2035* [Online]. Available: <https://www.zamstats.gov.zm/backup/phocadownload/Zambia> Census Projection 2011 - 2035.pdf [Accessed 24 May 2024].

ZHOU, Y., WEI, B., ZHANG, R. & LI, H. 2022. Evolution of water–energy–food–climate study: current status and future prospects. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 13, 463-481.

Appendices

Appendix I: CLEWs Model Development

A. Model Reference System

Land

To ensure adequate representation of crop diversity while capturing the predominant agricultural landscape, crops covering 80.4% of the total harvested area were selected for modelling, as illustrated in **Figure A.1** below.

Figure A.1. Displays the cumulative share of harvested crops (data source: (FAOSTAT, 2023))

The categories considered for land cover modelling encompass tree cover, artificial surfaces (built-up land), inland water (such as lakes and rivers), cropland, and other land, which consolidates all other categories into one. This distribution of land cover shown in **Figure A.2** is derived from a total area of 743,390 km² (OECD, 2024).

Figure A.2. illustrates the distribution of land cover in Zambia as of 2019 (data source: (OECD, 2024))

Within the model, 'Tree Cover' is represented by 'forests', 'Artificial Surfaces' by 'built-up' areas, 'Inland Water' by 'water', and 'Crop Land' by 'agriculture'. Additionally, the 'Other Land' category in the model comprises grassland, wetland, shrubland, sparse vegetation, and bare areas.

Energy

Regarding the energy mix incorporated in the model, in 2021, the total energy supply was approximately 500 PJ (IEA, 2021), distributed among various fuels, including coal, hydro, biofuels and waste, and oil, as shown in **Figure A.3**.

Figure A.3. Percentage share of total energy supply (data source: (IEA, 2021))

The sector-specific total final consumption is illustrated in **Table A.1**.

Table A.1. Total final consumption by sector (data source: (IEA, 2021))

Total Final Consumption	2019 (PJ)	% Share - 2019	2020 (PJ)	2021 (PJ)
Industry	78.44	22.11%	79.34	89.55
Transport	25.84	7.28%	26.57	35.18
Residential	238.09	67.11%	241.84	248.33
Commercial and public services	4.16	1.17%	4.10	4.19
Agriculture and forestry	2.35	0.66%	2.24	2.45
Non-specified	2.93	0.83%	3.11	2.42
Non energy use	2.97	0.84%	2.89	3.02
Total	354.78	100%	360.084	385.14

Water

There are three main water resources that need to be included in a reference CLEWs system: precipitation, groundwater, and surface water, as shown in **Table A.2** for 2020.

Table A.2. Reference system water distribution (data source: (FAO, 2024a))

Water Source	Volume (10 ⁹ m ³ /year)
Long-term average annual precipitation in volume	767.66
Total renewable groundwater	47.00
Total renewable surface water	104.80
Total renewable water	151.80
Agricultural water withdrawal	1.15
Industrial water withdrawal	0.13
Municipal water withdrawal	0.29
Total freshwater withdrawal	1.57

Understanding the threshold point for increased water demand is crucial for aligning opportunities and trade-offs within the nexus of sustainable growth. For instance, a regression analysis of the total population against total renewable water resources per capita, using data from the FAO AQUASTAT Dissemination System (FAO, 2024a) and assumptions in the sub-section C of **Appendix I**, yielded the graph presented in **Figure A.4**.

The projection indicating the year in which "Total Renewable Water Resources per Capita" becomes negative is particularly significant for the Zambian CLEWs model. This threshold could signal a critical

juncture at which the current system becomes unsustainable under the modelled conditions, as highlighted by the red line in the graph. This point could indicate several key issues:

- i. A negative value may suggest that the need for water resources surpasses the renewable supply, highlighting extreme water deficiency. This is a critical issue for Zambia, impacting agriculture, energy generation, and human health and welfare.
- ii. Identifying this year can provide essential information for policymakers, highlighting the urgency for immediate measures to decrease water usage or augment water supply through alternative methods such as water recycling or desalination.
- iii. In the CLEWs model, such a tipping point may signal increased strain on the entire system. This strain could affect energy generation and land utilisation and exacerbate climate change due to higher energy consumption for water extraction and treatment.

Figure A.4. Illustrating the relationship between population growth and total renewable water resources per capita

Addressing these concerns within the context of the Zambian CLEWs model is essential for developing strategies that ensure long-term sustainability and resilience against resource scarcity as presented in

Chapter 5.

B. Model Inputs and Outputs

Table B.1. and **Figure B.1.** below provide a comprehensive overview of the inputs and prospective outputs for the CLEWs model. This model integrates various aspects crucial for understanding and analysing the interdependencies and impacts within these systems.

Table B.1. Input and Output depiction of model

Model Component	Inputs	Outputs	Input Sources
Energy	Energy balance and energy demand projections	Optimal energy mix and capacity expansion	(ERB, 2024, IEA, 2021)
	Technology costs and efficiencies	Total energy system cost	(CCG, 2023, IRENA, 2023)
	Resource availability (e.g., fossil fuels, renewables)	Emissions (CO ₂ equivalent)	(CCG, 2023, IRENA, 2024)
	Climate data (wind, solar)	Energy security metrics	(Staffell and Pfenninger, 2016, World Bank, 2023)
	Policy scenarios		(MoE, 2022, MoE, 2024)
Land	Land use patterns (agriculture, forestry, urbanisation)	Land allocation for different uses	(OECD, 2024)
	Crop yields and water requirements	Agricultural productivity	(GAEZ, 2024, FAOSTAT, 2023)
	Land suitability	Land-use change impacts	(Kerner et al., 2024)
	Land tenure policies		(Sitko and Chamberlin, 2016)
	Crop cost data	Irrigated vs rainfed cultivation	(Frank, 2023)
Water	Water demand by sector (agriculture, industry, households)	Optimal water allocation	(FAO, 2024a)
	Water availability (surface water, groundwater)	Water scarcity indicators	(FAO, 2024a)
	Water infrastructure (dams, reservoirs)	Environmental flow requirements	(FAO, 2024a)
	water balance for use cases	Water balance (evapotranspiration, groundwater recharge and surface water)	(FAO, 2024a, FAO, 2024b)
Climate	Climate scenarios (temperature, precipitation, extreme events)	Climate impact assessments (e.g., crop yield changes, water availability)	(GAEZ, 2024, Stadtbäumer et al., 2022)
	Historical climate data	Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies	(World Bank, 2024)
	Emission factors	Emissions linked to energy, water, and land use and land use change	(CCG, 2023)

Figure B.1. Illustrating CLEWs model inputs and outputs

C. Model Assumptions

Demographic and Economic

GDP – Historic and Projected

Historic GDP projections for Zambia were derived from a combination of sources, primarily utilising data from the World Bank and the Zambia Statistics Agency. According to World Bank data, Zambia's GDP for 2022 amounted to \$29.78 billion, reflecting a significant increase of 34.48% compared to 2021. In 2021, Zambia's GDP stood at \$22.15 billion, marking a 22.29% increase from the previous year. However, in 2020, Zambia experienced a downturn with a GDP of \$18.11 billion, representing a substantial decline of 22.3% from 2019. Similarly, in 2019, Zambia's GDP was recorded at \$23.31 billion, indicating an 11.41% decrease from 2018 (**Macrotrends, 2024**).

In 2020, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) predicted a severe -3.5% contraction in Zambia's GDP, attributing this decline to the pandemic's global economic impact and volatile commodity prices (**IMF, 2020**). At the same time, 'The Economist' offered a slightly more pessimistic view, predicting a 3.8% contraction in Zambia's economy for the same period (**ERB, 2022**). However, the African Development Bank predicted GDP growth of 4.0% in 2023 and 4.2% in 2024, spurred by recovery in mining, services, and manufacturing, and rising global copper prices (**AFDB, 2023**).

The proposed preliminary GDP assumptions for the **CLEWs Zambia** model are illustrated in **Table C.1**.

Table C.1. GDP growth scenarios (sources: (Macrotrends, 2024, IMF, 2020, ERB, 2022, World Bank, 2022))

Scenarios	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025 - 50	Comments
Base	-3.5%	2.3%	3.7%	4.6%	5.5%	3.5%	2020 and 2021 data from IMF Report. 2022 data from World Bank MPO. The Economist Intelligence Unit projects 5.5% for 2024. From 2025, historical average growth of 3.5% per year (2014-2018).
Low	-3.8%	2.3%	2.3%	2.3%	2.3%	2.7%	2020: Economist reports contraction. 2021-2024: IMF forecasts growth. Post-2025: GDP matches population growth.
High	1.6%	2.3%	3.7%	5.5%	5.5%	5.0%	2020-2022 data from MPO. The Economist projects 5.5% annual growth for 2023-2024. Sustained 5% growth thereafter, slightly below the 2010-2018 annual GDP growth of 5.2%.

Projected Population

The population growth forecast for the years 2019 to 2035 relies on ZamStats data (**ZambStats, 2013**). Subsequently, for the period spanning 2035 to 2050, projections are drawn from the World Population Review dataset (**WPR, 2024**). This forecast is summarised in **Table C.2.**, which presents a more conservative population growth compared to that shown in **Figure A.4**.

Table C.2. Zambia Census Population Projection 2019-2050

POPULATION	2019	2020	2025	2030	2035	2050
Total	17,381,168	17,885,422	20,574,138	3,576,214	26,923,658	37,500,00
% per annum	2.9%	2.9%	2.8%	2.8%	2.7%	1.84%

Energy Demand Projections

The energy demand projections by sector and fuel are illustrated in **Figure C.1.** and **Figure C.2.**, respectively.

Figure C.1. Sector-specific energy demand projections (2019-2050)

Figure C.2. Energy demand projections by fuel (2019-2050)

Water Demand Projections

The water distribution ratios for evapotranspiration, groundwater recharge, and surface runoff are presented in **Table C.3**.

Table C.3. Water ratios for evapotranspiration, groundwater recharge & surface run-off (source: (FAO, 2024b))

Component	Category	Evapotranspiration	Groundwater Recharge	Surface Runoff
		WTREVT	WTRGWT	WTRSUR
Maize	Rainfed	48.0%	2.6%	49.4%
Maize	Irrigated	21.4%	3.9%	74.6%
Groundnut	Rainfed	42.0%	2.9%	55.1%
Groundnut	Irrigated	18.2%	4.1%	77.7%
Soybean	Rainfed	36.0%	3.2%	60.8%
Soybean	Irrigated	24.7%	3.8%	71.6%
Sorghum	Rainfed	41.0%	3.0%	56.1%
Sorghum	Irrigated	14.0%	4.3%	81.7%
Sugarcane	Rainfed	18.0%	4.1%	77.9%
Sugarcane	Irrigated	38.0%	3.1%	58.9%
Cassava	Rainfed	31.0%	3.5%	65.6%
Cassava	Irrigated	16.9%	4.2%	79.0%
Cotton	Rainfed	56.0%	2.2%	41.8%
Cotton	Irrigated	18.8%	4.1%	77.1%
Rice	Rainfed	56.0%	2.2%	41.8%
Rice	Irrigated	20.5%	4.0%	75.6%
Wheat	Rainfed	24.0%	3.8%	72.2%
Wheat	Irrigated	9.1%	4.5%	86.4%
Forest		71%	2.50%	26.50%
Built up land		63%	3%	34%
Water bodies		33%	7%	60%
Other		71%	2%	27%

Figure C.3. illustrates the water demand projection for public consumption. The demand from agriculture and cooling for power plants is presented in **Chapter 4**, as it is a function of the CLEWs interlinkages and provided as model output results.

Figure C.3. Water demand projection per consumption sector

Crop Demand Projections

The demand for the nine-modelled crops is shown in **Figure C.4.** below.

Figure C.4. Crop demand projections

Appendix II: Detailed Stakeholder Interactions and Collected Data

Farmer Questionnaire

Research Questionnaire where the researcher with the help of Green Belt Energy interviews the Commercial and Subsistence Farmers for the research Enhancing Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development in Zambia: An Integrated Model. Baseline 2019, Projections to 2050.

Thank you for participating in this interview. Your insights are invaluable for understanding and addressing critical issues related to sustainable development in Zambia, particularly concerning agriculture, food security, and energy. This interview is conducted by Greenbelt Energy (on behalf of **Kumbuso Joshua Nyoni**) to gather essential data from commercial and subsistence farmers, for the research project titled "Enhancing Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development in Zambia: An Integrated Model." Your responses will help analyse resource management, identify synergies, and manage trade-offs within the energy-climate-food-water nexus.

- 1) *Please provide an overview of the current challenges and opportunities related to sustainable development in Zambia, particularly in the context of agriculture, food security, and energy, from the perspective of your farming experience.*
- 2) *Zambia is currently facing challenges such as drought, affecting food security, water availability, and energy security. How do you believe we can improve planning for the future to ensure measures are in place to mitigate risks, account for climate change, and better manage available resources without implicating other areas?*
- 3) *The research focuses on understanding the relationships within the nexus of energy, food, climate, and water. Could you share your insights on the importance of governance and public policies in fostering sustainable development in Zambia, particularly in managing vital resources such as energy, climate, water, and land, based on your farming experience?*
- 4) *Zambia faces water quality risks due to various factors, including agricultural practices, hydropower development, and urbanisation. From your perspective, what are the key challenges and priorities in addressing these risks, and how do you perceive the need for sustainable investments in this regard?*
- 5) *We aim to gather data on crop costs (capital, variable, fixed costs) for various crops (rainfed and irrigated) in Zambia. Please provide information using the template provided, including the baseline year.*
 - What crops are currently being cultivated and why?
 - Reasons for cultivating specific crops and the primary demand drivers.
 - Crop Type:

- Baseline Year for Data:
- Capital Costs (per hectare):
- Variable Costs (per hectare):
- Fixed Costs (per hectare):

6) *Please feel free to provide any additional insights, comments, or observations related to sustainable development, agriculture, or resource management in Zambia, based on your farming experience.*

Actual Questionnaire Responses by a Farmer Named Fredson

Answer 1: *"The challenge has been on soils, which we are using. What I mean is that, for example, at my small farm, you find that the area itself may have about, maybe three to four types of soils within the small farm, which is just about 80 acres. So usually, as small-scale farmers, we rarely take ourselves, say, protesting to know to say, okay, in this particular area, my field, what is their source? What the kind of nutrients required supposed to be so much? In addition, all this probably is because we have just gotten so used to the use of these synthetic fertilizers and the like. As a result, we have found that most of the nutrients have been eroded away, so to say. Therefore, for that to meet in terms of production or sustainability, to meet the required production always has been a challenge".*

Answer 2: *"I think on that one I will still take you back to conservation farming. Conservation farming has been found to especially where there is less, for example, the past season. The past season which we aware we face this not having enough requirement.*

You find that those who did the conservation channel where organic fertilizers were used, the simple manure, for example, from the manure and the like. when I look at what you are doing using that and all that kind of stuff, at least all that kind of fertilizer actually holds the moisture. As a result, you find that most of the crops, which we have grown, are under such find that the crop did well despite not having enough rain because of organic fertilizers so for me, When I look at the economic aspect of it, use of such kind of appraisals like the organic fertilizer you are used during the conservation farming itself.

That is the way, that is the future we can still hold as compared to say, since we don't have this, we will just pay also, even when we want to talk about irrigation. Yes, irrigation grows with the availability of water, much as you would want to use irrigation, for example. I am using that now that I'm doing a bit of winter maize. However, you find that in the end the water level actually will below the requirement. As a result, we still have those challenges. However, use of this and without that kind of conservation farming, you may not as well attain the required youth as it ends. So that's where I'm also looking at that."

Answer 3: *"I think the policies, in terms of the government policies really have to come in this situation because imagine running any business without planning, without management in it, without having a policy on how to do it. Definitely, you have no direction. So the government policy in this case, for me, it's quite hard, you know, because it's only through them that, for example, the people had grown, for example, maize had grown quite a lot. But with the kind of rainfall that did not do very well. So that calls for the government to come in. How are they going to help the masses? It was not their own wish.*

Experience, we already know that now we have climate change. And it's for that reason that we really have to plan for such eventualities. Therefore, the government has to look into that as a policy to say, should we have such eventualities, we need to have planned so that we are completely ready. Do not leave our people behind. So those are some of the things I think policy management and all that kind of thing. We need to look back".

Answer 4: *"I will start with the agriculture practice. I think I always refer to the small-scale farmers because this is where we actually get the huge production or application from them to feed the country. However, you find that most of the agricultural practices, which have been done, are still essence. Okay. What I mean is that I come from southern province by tribe. You find that area like southern province, all the trees or the forest as it were, just to clear and clear to. Just to make those shoots without, you know, like replanting, planting trees. As a result, most of the southern province is one of the areas, which is usually hit when it comes to this climate change. Because of the agricultural practices which would have been using in that area.*

However, in the area mentioned that one of the avenues we can try now, despite that things have already been destroyed. It is the same congregation panel where we. I will still talk about it. Where we need to use this organic fertilizer, as it were, that we are able to enrich the source bug and hold on the moisture, which is required.

Hydropower development, yes. Is required in terms of the irrigation system, which I think is being promoted now. In Zambia, we are told that we have about 40% of water. When you look at these rivers, which we have, but for such a long time we have never thought of developing that to that levels where at the end of the day we are able to use the irrigated water throughout the year in terms of production to develop the alone. Okay. So I think now I have seen the government has been some advocates and what even the private sector trying to come in to see how they can mitigate that, okay. By bringing in this equipment and like doing the boreholes. Simply to help those who want to go into irrigation".

Answer 5: *"In Zambia, to be honest, the major crop has always been maize as a staple food. But as cash crops had cotton, which to me it has gone down. I do not know the challenge, which would have*

been there either. The market price could have been a determinant on that. There have been also tobacco as a cash crop. When you talk of coffee, you talk of these other. I have been more on the commercial side, but my friends always have been on the small scale. Soybeans also had an uprising for the past five years. Now, of course, prices have changed over time. Of course, as a result of demand and supply. We find that maybe when the demand is high, the prices also are on a higher side and price. So I think those are some of the problems with small-scale farmers have been doing in the country”.

Answer 6: *“In terms of agriculture sustainability, I always want to promote. I’m trying to refer to this, what we call interested farming. I’m sure you’ll be heard about that. This is where as a farmer is depending on either the government to help us with these synthetic fertilizers and all that kind of stuff. If this particular farmer is able, for example to keep some animals, let’s say for example maybe pigs, the pigs will produce the pig droppings. Okay. The fecal matter, you have the pigs here you have the fish. On the other side, fish ponds. Then you are doing maybe your orchard or maybe you are doing your garden. Okay. On the other side you may have some chickens, okay. Yeah. The droppings of this livestock stuff can either be used for feeding the fish.*

Or they can also be used it as manure in the orchard or in the garden, larger scale in your crop production serenity, for example, you can use those droppings. It goes around like that. Okay. Where the production from the same mesh, for example, or from the crop, you make some kind of hay where you can use to feed the same pigs or to feed the cow or the pigs, it goes around like that. The same droppings also can be used as slurry or in terms of producing gas”.

Other questionnaire responses and reactions from other stakeholders have been uploaded on the Zenodo⁵³ repository as seen in Appendix III below.

⁵³ Zenodo is a versatile open repository created as part of the European OpenAIRE initiative and managed by CERN.

Data Collected from Stakeholders

RAINFED MAIZE PRODUCTION FOR 2023/2024 SEASON/HECTARE

Source: Farmers Stakeholder Analysis, 2024

S/N	Item	Description	Quantity	Variable Costs	Fixed Costs
1	Seed- Pannar 53	Always choose the best seed for the region	20-Kilogram (KGs)	K860.0 2*K430.0	NILL
2	Fertilizers	Basal and Top dressing or its equivalence	4 Bags D Compound 4 Bags Urea	K9,600.0 50Kg*K1,200	NILL
3	Weed killers/Herbicides *Pre-emergence *Post Emergence	Recommended one related to weed type, size etc.	*4-KGs Glysphate non-selective *5-litres Force; Selective	*K600.0 1Kg*K150.0 *K925.0 1Lr*K185.0	NILL
4	Pesticides *Benzo 1.9% *Bolt 315.4EW	For Pests such as armyworms	*2- Liters *1.4 –Liters	K350.0 1L*K175.0 K280.0 700ml*K140.0	NILL
5	Lime *Liquid Lime *Micronized Lime	Returns Soil pH from Acidity to the recommended pH of maize	*5-Litres *5- Kilograms (KGs)	K1,500.0 1Lt*K300.0 K1,500.0 100g*K30.0	NILL

6	*Infinity Fertilizers *Soil Analysis	Supplies macro-elements not capacities in the Main fertilizers	2 Liters *Early spraying(1lr) *Late Spraying(1lr)	K2,800.0 4(500ml) *K700.0 *K450.0/Ha	NILL
7	*Labor *Ground Rates	Dependable location /Resources available	*Tractor Ploughing. *Cattle ploughing. *Planting *Spraying *Harvesting	*K2,000.0 *K1,000.0 *K250.0 *K500.0 *K500.0	*Ground Rates= K85.0 Annually Leased for 4Ha
8	*Transportation	Depends on the available market for product selling.		K2,000.0 *(Movements to and from city/farm)	NILL
9	TOTAL			K23,335.00	K85.0

SOYA BEANS PRODUCTION FOR 2023/2024 SEASON /HECTARE

S/N	Item	Description	Quantity	Variable Costs	Fixed Costs
1	Seed	Dependent of choice /region/rainfall pattern e.g. Dina/Kafue/Spike	100KGs seed / Hectare	K3,600.0 4(25kg)*K900 *Dina Seed	NILL
2	Granular Fertilizer	Recommend soya mix A	4 Bags of Soya Mix	K3,400.0 4(50Kg)*K850.0	NILL
3	Infinity Fertilizer	Recommended without Granular Fertilizer	1litre Sprayed @2 occasions	K2,800.0 4(500ml)*K700	NILL

4	Weed Killers/ Herbicides	Non selective Glysophate/ Pre-emergency	4KGs/ Glysophate	K600.0 4(1Kg)*K150.0	NILL
5.	Selective Herbicides/ Weed Killers	Aloxyforce for post emergency mainly after germination.	5Litres /Ha	K800.0 5(1Lr)*K160.0	NILL
6	Lime	*Micronized *Liquid	*5KGs/Ha *5Ltrs/Ha	Please refer to table one. NB;Choose one	NILL
7.	Insecticides	Used to control pests/insects;	*Lambdex 400mls/Ha *Benzo Extra 800g/Ha	*K360.0 2*K180.0 *K320.0 2*K160.0 NB;Choose one	NILL
8	Fungicides	*Warrior 72wp *Mancozeb	*4KGs/Ha *4KGs/Ha	*K800.0 4(1Kg)*K200.0 *K880.0 4(1Kg)*K220.0 NB;Choose one	NILL
9	*Labour	Land preparation cardinal ;Labours costs are dependable of locality	*Tractor Ploughing *Furrow Ploughing *Planting *Harvesting *Transportation	*K2,000.0 *K1000.0 *K500.0 *K1,000.0 *K2,000.0	Land lease K85.0 Annually
10	TOTAL			K18,940.0	K85.0

AVERAGE ANNUAL PRODUCTION OF CROPS IN ZAMBIA FOR THE PERIOD 2008–2018

Source: FAO, 2014

Rank	Crop Production (tons)	Area Harvested (ha)	Yield (tons/ha)
1 Sugarcane	3 295 910	33 501	98.38
2 Maize	2 728 868	1 097 809	2.49
3 Cassavas	1 580 794	135 283	11.69
4 Wheat	214 461	33 568	6.39
5 Soybeans	200 231	118 632	1.69
6 Sweet Potatoes	160 750	46 671	3.44
7 Groundnuts	127 141	206 415	0.62
8 Cotton	120 640	139 349	0.87
9 Cashew Nuts	85 609	1 449	59.07
10 Tobacco	48 624	49 845	0.98
11 Rice	44 534	33 524	1.33
12 Irish Potatoes	41 864	17 709	2.36
13 Millet	39 067	40 414	0.97
14 Sunflower	33 508	62 958	0.53
15 Sorghums	16 727	20 902	0.8
16 Barley	10 775	1 459	7.39

Top 5 Crops by Production Volume and Nutritional Value (adapted from the BEFS Assessment)

Source: FAO, 2014

Sugarcane	Crop Production (tons)	Hectares	Yield	Food Supply (kcal/cap/day)	Percentage
Maize	3,295,910	33,501	98.38	174	7.8
Cassava	2,728,868	1,097,809	2.49	738	33
Wheat	1,580,794	135,283	11.69	504	23
Soyabean	214,461	33,568	6.39	206	9.2

Appendix III: Model and Data Repository

The relevant data for modelling and research is summarised in the table below and uploaded on the Zenodo and Github repositories.

Model And Data Repository	Description	Author	Repository Link
GeoCLEWs Outputs	Tabular results in CSV format compatible with CLEWs modelling using OSeMOSYS. Interactive graphs for visualization and analysis. GEOCLEWs for Zambia titled 'CLEWs-ZMB-2024' on GitHub.	(Nyoni, 2024a)	GitHub Link ⁵⁴
GeoCLEWs Script	The script GeoCLEWs_ZM automates data collection from GAEZ v4 and FAOSTAT, processing agro-climatic potential yield, crop water deficit, precipitation, and land cover. Outputs can be combined with electricity information for detailed CLEWs modelling. Successfully tested on Windows machines.	(Nyoni, 2024a)	GitHub Link
Detailed Stakeholder Responses	Detailed responses from stakeholders.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link ⁵⁵
Detailed CLEWs Crop, Land, Water Modelling Input File	Excel file uploaded on Zenodo.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link
CLEWs Model Data File (BAU Scenario)	Text file for the Business as Usual scenario.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link
CLEWs Model Data File (No Adaptation Scenario)	Text file for the No Adaptation scenario.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link
CLEWs Model Data File (Climate Adjusted Infrastructure Scenario)	Text file for the Climate Adjusted Infrastructure scenario.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link
CLEWs Model Data File (Biofuel Adoption Scenario)	Text file for the Biofuel Adoption scenario.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link
CLEWs Model Data File (Increased Agriculture Scenario)	Text file for the Increased Agriculture scenario.	(Nyoni, 2024b)	Zenodo Link

⁵⁴ <https://github.com/Kumbutso-Bird/CLEWs-ZMB-2024>

⁵⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/12585995>